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EVALUATION DESIGN AND PLAN REPORT

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GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS

AARP	American Association of Retired Persons
BIA	Budget Impact Analysis
CDSE	Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy
CDSMP	Chronic Disease Self-Management Programme
EFFICHRONIC	enhancing health systems sustainability by providing (cost-) EFFECTiveness data of an evidenced-based Intervention for CHRONIC management in citizens with a low socioeconomic status
EQ-5D-5L	EuroQoL- 5 Dimensions - 5 Levels
Fr	France
HLQ	Health Literacy Questionnaire
HR-QoL	Health-Related Quality of Life
ICER	Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
ICPC	International Classification of Primary Care
It	Italy
IPAQ	International Physical Activity Questionnaire
MPI	Multidimensional Prognostic Index
NL	The Netherlands
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PPPs	Purchasing Power Parities
PCQ	Productivity Costs Questionnaire
PHQ	Patient Health Questionnaire
SD	Standard Deviation
SEP	Socio Economic Position
SF	Short-Form
SFES	Social-Familial Evaluation Scale
SMAQ	Short Medication Adherence Questionnaire
SMRC	Self-Management Resource Center
Sp	Spain
UK	United Kingdom
WHO	World Health Organization

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Chronic Disease Self-Management Programme (CDSMP) intervention is an evidence-based program for adults with a chronic condition to encourage them to better manage and maintain their health status. The CDSMP intervention is expected to achieve greater health gains in vulnerable citizens with a low socioeconomic position (SEP), because their disease progression is less favourable and their adoption of healthy habits lower compared to citizens with a higher SEP. In the EFFICHRONIC project, pilot sites in five European countries implemented the CDSMP intervention. The main aim was to appraise the CDSMP intervention in terms of benefits for the target population by answering the following research questions:

1. What are the benefits of the CDSMP intervention for the target population in terms of self-management in healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, adherence to medications and Health-Related Quality of Life (HR-QoL)?
2. What are the effects of the CDSMP intervention for the target population on health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and prevalence of experienced medical errors?
3. What are the societal cost savings of the CDSMP intervention in terms of reducing healthcare utilization and productivity losses among the target population?
4. To what extent is the target population satisfied with the CDSMP intervention as a whole as well as with specific elements (problem solving, decision making, and confidence building)?

Using a 6-month pre-post design, more than 2750 citizens ≥ 18 years of age with a chronic condition and a low SEP and their caregivers were invited to participate in the project's intervention. The CDSMP intervention was implemented in five pilot sites: the region of Rotterdam in the Netherlands, region of Occitanie in France, province of Genoa in Italy, principality of Asturias in Spain and regions throughout the United Kingdom. Participants who attended at least four of the six sessions of the CDSMP intervention (n=2277) were eligible for the evaluation study. A total of 1825 completed the baseline questionnaire, of which 1189 completed also the questionnaire at follow-up.

The CDSMP intervention resulted in improvements in several outcome measures, including self-management, swimming, sedentary behaviour, alcohol use, depressive symptoms and HR-QoL. Significant improvements were also found for health literacy (understanding information), communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors. The improvements with regard to health outcomes, health behaviours and health literacy in the total sample were not always observed in exploratory subgroup analyses. Most effects were more pronounced in women and in younger participants (<65 y).

The cost-effectiveness of the CDSMP intervention was studied from both a healthcare perspective and a societal perspective. **The change in health utility was +0.015 points (on a 0.0 to 1.0 scale). After 6 months, the intervention resulted in a mean saving of 307 euro per participant in healthcare costs. For productivity costs, this was 473 euro per participant (260 euro from lost productivity at paid work; 267 euro from lost productivity at unpaid work). When combining these costs (societal perspective), the total saving is 780 euro per participant.** The calculation of the saving cost is based on the total sample size of participants engaged by the whole consortium which gives a significant result.

Satisfaction of the participants was assessed after the intervention period of 6 months. **Overall, the participants were positive over the CDSMP programme.**

To conclude, as part of the EFFICHRONIC project, the 6-month CDSMP intervention in persons with a chronic condition with a low SEP or their caregivers showed benefits on several relevant outcome measures in the five pilot sites. The intervention resulted in a mean saving of 780 euro in societal costs per participant, and participants' satisfaction with the CDSMP intervention was high. Future studies on the CDSMP programme in populations with a low SEP are warranted.

PURPOSE, OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), around 35% of women and 29% of men are affected by chronic conditions - mainly cardiovascular diseases, cancers, chronic respiratory diseases and diabetes [1, 2]. This percentage is clearly influenced by both modifiable risk factors (such as physical exercise, smoking, alcohol use, stress and unhealthy diets) and socioeconomic, cultural and environmental determinants [2, 3]. The high prevalence of chronic conditions put a large burden on national budgets. The healthcare costs of chronic conditions reach 7% of Gross Domestic Product in some European countries [4, 5]. Additionally, chronic conditions affect the active population by reducing their productivity and competitiveness. Fortunately, in addition to specific drug therapy, chronic conditions can be prevented or controlled by reducing risk factors [2].

Within this context of overloaded healthcare systems, the ability of citizens with a chronic condition to be self-sufficient for as long as possible has become increasingly important. The Chronic Disease Self-Management Programme (CDSMP) intervention was developed specifically to encourage citizens with a chronic condition to better manage their health and maintain their health status [6]. This evidence-based program was developed 40 years ago at Stanford University (the United States) and has since been implemented effectively in general populations of more than 20 countries (e.g. Australia, China, UK, Canada, Italy, Denmark and Hispanic countries such as Spain, Argentina, Colombia, Chile, Peru and Costa Rica). The CDSMP intervention consists of a series of 6 tightly scripted workshops, 2.5 hours each, which are held once a week for 6 weeks. The intervention is designed to be delivered by two lay-persons who have been trained for that purpose and who have a chronic condition themselves (i.e. peers). One of the persons who deliver the intervention can also be a trained healthcare or social care professional. The intervention is attended by a group of people with different chronic conditions; voluntary caregivers of people with a chronic condition can also participate. The workshops focus on several topics including healthy lifestyle, emotions and medication adherence. The program is based on the self-efficacy theory and emphasizes problem solving, decision making and confidence building [7, 8].

Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of the CDSMP intervention in improving self-management [9-12]. Overall, these studies show that the intervention led to more physical exercise, less health distress, better self-care and a beneficial effect on self-efficacy measures [9]. However, there is scientific evidence that the socioeconomic position (SEP) of citizens affects the development of chronic conditions and the adoption of habits and lifestyles [13-16]. The CDSMP intervention is expected to achieve greater health gains in citizens with a low SEP, because their disease progression is less favourable and their adoption of healthy habits lower compared to citizens with a higher SEP. Citizens with a low SEP have more adverse chronic conditions and fewer opportunities and possibilities to adhere to healthy habits [2]. At the same time, they are less likely and often less interested in participating in community-based interventions, training programmes and research actions [17, 18].

The EFFICHRONIC Project

The EFFICHRONIC project was set up to implement the CDSMP intervention specifically in citizens ≥ 18 years of age with a chronic condition and with a low SEP and their caregivers (the target population). In the project, pilot sites in five European countries implemented the CDSMP intervention: the region of Rotterdam in the Netherlands, region of Occitanie in France, province of Genoa in Italy, principality of Asturias in Spain and regions throughout the United Kingdom. **EFFICHRONIC aims to empower the target population to self-manage their chronic conditions through an integrated approach, gathering citizens suffering with a variety of chronic conditions, and evaluating (cost-) effectiveness. This information will allow for the adoption of policies for the prevention and management of chronic conditions to achieve more sustainable health outcomes.**

Objectives

The main objective of the evaluation study was to appraise the CDSMP intervention in terms of benefits for the target population. The following objectives / research questions were answered:

1. What are the benefits of the CDSMP intervention for the target population in terms of **self-management in healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, adherence to medications and Health-Related Quality of Life (HR-QoL)**?
2. What are the effects of the CDSMP intervention for the target population on **health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and prevalence of experienced medical errors**?
3. What are the **societal cost savings** of the CDSMP intervention in terms of reducing healthcare utilization and productivity losses among the target population?
4. To what extent is the target population **satisfied with the CDSMP intervention** as a whole as well as with specific elements (problem solving, decision making, and confidence building)?

In this deliverable the following topics are included:

- the description of the study sample;
- an overview of the data regarding the study participants at the baseline measurement, and at the follow-up measurement; especially the data collection carried out from M6 to M39;
- the description of the comprehensive framework for the impact assessment in order to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of the investment (health economics techniques are applied for this purpose).

Study hypotheses

We hypothesized that the intervention would provide participants with a greater ability to self-manage their chronic condition, a more favourable lifestyle, less depression, a reduction in sleep problems and fatigue, greater adherence to medication and a more favourable HR-QoL. We also hypothesized that the intervention would reduce the prevalence of experienced medical errors and improve the communication with healthcare providers and health literacy. We furthermore hypothesized that society would benefit from the intervention through a reduced use of healthcare resources and greater productivity. We hypothesized to reach a satisfaction score of 7 or higher on a 1–10 scale for the CDSMP intervention, with higher scores representing greater satisfaction.

METHODOLOGY

Design, setting and procedures

The evaluation design and plan report have been described in D6.1 Evaluation design and plan report. In short, the evaluation study has a pre-post design. Participants were recruited in accordance with the capacity, organizational and contextual factors of each of the five pilot sites (see D5.1 CDSMP Implementation plan). The target population consists of vulnerable citizens ≥ 18 years of age with a chronic condition and a low SEP as well as their caregivers, who are expected to be able to participate in the study for at least 6 months. Citizens were not eligible to participate when they were not able to understand the information provided in the language of the country of residence, were experiencing a period of crisis, their basic housing needs were not met, were diagnosed with severe unstable mental health problems or suffered from active addictive disorders or cognitive decline. Data have been collected from participants before the start of the first workshop session (baseline; T0) and at 6 months (follow-up; T1) [19]. Written consent was acquired from all participants, and the study protocol was approved by the Ethical Review Boards of four of the five pilot sites (it was not needed in the UK).

Data collection and measures

Data collection was done with the use of a questionnaire, including primary and secondary outcome measures. The baseline questionnaire and follow-up questionnaire are included in Annex 1 and Annex 2, respectively. Instruments used for the outcome measures have been described in D6.1 Evaluation design and plan report and are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of outcome measures in the EFFICHRONIC questionnaire

	Instrument	T0	T1
Objective 1			
self-management	short 6-item Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument (CDSE-6)[8]	X	X
healthy lifestyle			
physical exercise	6 items on physical exercise (developed specifically for the Stanford CDSMP intervention)[8]	X	X
healthy eating	3 items on intake of fruits, vegetables, and breakfast	X	X
sedentary behaviour	1 item from the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ)[20]	X	X
smoking	1 item	X	X
alcohol use	1 item from the AUDIT-C[21]	X	X
depression	8-item Patient Health Questionnaire depression scale (PHQ-8)[22]	X	X
sleep	visual analog scale (developed specifically for the Stanford CDSMP intervention)[8]	X	X
fatigue	visual analog scale (developed specifically for the Stanford CDSMP intervention)[8]	X	X
adherence to medications	short 6-item Medication Adherence Questionnaire (SMAQ)[23]	X	X
HR-QoL	12-item short-form (SF-12)[24] EQ-5D-5L instrument[25]	X	X
Objective 2			
health literacy	2 items from the Health Literacy Questionnaire (HLQ)[26]	X	X
communication with healthcare providers	a scale of 3 items measuring the change in key behaviours concerning communicating with healthcare providers (developed by the Self-Management Resource Center; SMRC)[27]	X	X
prevalence of experienced medical errors	3 items from the American Association of Retired Persons (AARP) 'survey beyond 50.09' questionnaire	X	X
Objective 3			

healthcare utilization	4 items from the SMRC Health Care Utilization questionnaire regarding doctor appointments, the use of hospital emergency room visits and hospitalised nights.[28]	X	X
productivity losses	2 domains from the Productivity Costs Questionnaire (PCQ)[29]: Lost productivity at paid work due to absenteeism (6 items) and lost productivity at unpaid work (3 items).	X	X
Objective 4			
experienced improvement	On most days I do at least one activity to improve my health I do not let my health problems control my life Did the programme improve you in being able to make decisions? Did the programme improve you in being able to express yourself? Did the programme improve the communication with your family, friends and/or others? Did the programme improve your confidence in the health system understanding your needs?		X
satisfaction	On a scale from 0-10 how satisfied were you with the CDSMP intervention?		X

In addition, various sociodemographic characteristics were measured, including age, sex, country of birth, educational level, employment situation, household composition and income. Any additional remarks could be left in an open box at the end of the questionnaire.

Data management and statistical analysis

Data from all pilot sites were combined, and data-management and analysis were done at the Erasmus MC University Medical Center. Paper questionnaires were transferred into electronic files and checked for missing or incorrect data. If an error was present in the electronic data, paper questionnaires were consulted. When needed, responsible staff were contacted for clarification. Data cleaning and analyses were performed in June to September of 2020. All data was handled confidentially and scientific data is stored anonymously.

Statistical analyses were conducted with the statistical software program SPSS for Windows version 24.0. In all cases $P < 0.05$ was taken as statistically significant.

Descriptives

Descriptive statistics (mean \pm SD or N(%)) were used to summarize characteristics of participants in the total study population and in each pilot site. Sociodemographic characteristics at baseline were compared between the pilot sites using ANOVA (for continuous variables) and chi-square test (for categorical variables).

Objective 1 and 2

Descriptive statistics of the outcome measures at baseline in the total study population and in each pilot site were performed. Furthermore, changes between T0 and T1 measurements were assessed by means of the paired T test (for continuous variables showing a normal distribution) or the McNemar test (for categorical variables). In addition, the 6-month change analyses were repeated in several stratified analyses: by sex and age. Since the outbreak of the COVID-19 virus happened before the follow-up measurement of a part of the participants, we also stratified the analyses by whether the follow-up questionnaire was filled in before or after the COVID-19 outbreak. We used different dates in March 2020 as cutoff for the outbreak for each pilot site, according to lockdown measures: the Netherlands: 16 March, France: 17 March, Italy: 11 March, Spain: 14 March, and the UK: 16 March (this date or later was defined as 'after the outbreak').

Objective 3

Using the baseline measurement as control group, a preliminary cost-effectiveness analysis was performed from a healthcare and societal perspective and with a time horizon of 6 months. For the healthcare perspective, healthcare costs for individual participants were determined by multiplying resource use (doctor appointments, hospital emergency room visits and hospitalised nights) with corresponding unit prices for 2017. We used the year 2017 because the project commenced in that year; however, the differences with values of 2018 or 2019 are expected to be minimal. For the societal perspective, productivity losses for individual participants (lost productivity at paid work due to absenteeism and lost productivity at unpaid work) followed from multiplying lost (un)paid hours from the PCQ with corresponding hourly costs for 2017. As the PCQ has a recall time of 4 weeks, productivity costs per participant were extrapolated to reflect 6 months by dividing the obtained 4-week productivity costs by 4 and multiplying it by 26 (weeks). Utility values were obtained through the EQ-5D-5L instrument [25]. The English questionnaire was used, not only in the UK but also in the other four pilot sites (after translation). For the analyses, the syntax of this English version including the English value set was used.

Finally, a budget impact analysis (BIA) estimated the financial consequences of implementing the intervention. A BIA is very valuable in supporting the adoption of policies for the prevention of chronic conditions because they take accessibility and affordability constraints into account when considering cost effectiveness. To estimate the societal cost savings (or economic burden) of the CDSMP intervention, the mean societal costs per participant were extrapolated to the prevalence of the target population in respective countries.

Objective 4

At follow-up (T1), participants were asked about the CDSMP intervention and their experienced changes in the months after participation. Descriptives statistics were performed.

RESULTS

Recruitment and retention

The recruitment of people to participate in the intervention was not easy in most pilot sites. Therefore, the project was given a 6-month extension to still meet the statistical power as described in the evaluation design article [30]. For that purpose, at least 978 questionnaires had to be collected at follow-up. In 2020, the unstable situation caused by the COVID-19 outbreak worldwide was an additional challenge for the final stages of data collection. The sites applied the necessary means to optimize participation in the study and to collect the follow-up questionnaires, such as written and telephone reminders.

Table 2 shows the numbers of recruited persons and valid questionnaires at baseline and follow-up. Among all participating sites, **2759 patients or caregivers were recruited for participation** in the project and attended at least 1 out of six sessions of the CDSMP intervention ('engaged participants'). Of them, **2277 attended at least four of the six sessions** ('completed participants'). **A total of 1825 valid baseline questionnaires were collected and 1189 valid follow-up questionnaires**, by July 31st 2020. This meets the requirement of a sample size (at least 978 follow-up questionnaires) to ensure statistical power. **The overall retention rate of questionnaires was 65.2%**, ranging from 59.3% in France to 79.7% in the UK.

Table 2. Data collection overview (recruited participants and valid questionnaires) for the total sample and according to pilot site

	Total	Pilot site				
		NL	Fr	It	Sp	UK
Engaged participants (signed up and attended ≥ 1 of 6 sessions)	2759	417	234	400	1131	577
Completed participants (attended ≥ 4 of 6 sessions)	2277	363	196	284	932	502
Baseline questionnaire (T0)*	1825	388	209	324	559	345
Follow-up questionnaire (T1)*	1189	247	124	200	343	275
<i>Retention of questionnaires (%)</i>	65.2	63.7	59.3	61.7	61.4	79.7

Abbreviations: Fr, France; It, Italy; NL, the Netherlands; Sp, Spain; UK, the United Kingdom

* Received questionnaires until July 31st 2020.

Characteristics study population

The baseline sociodemographic characteristics of all participants who filled in the baseline questionnaire (n=1825) are presented in Table 3a, for the total group and by pilot site. The mean age was 59.6 (14.9) years and 69.6% were female. Comparison between pilot sites shows that all characteristics were significantly different ($P < 0.001$).

The baseline sociodemographic characteristics of participants who filled in both the baseline questionnaire and follow-up questionnaire (n=1189) are presented in Table 3b, for the total group and by pilot site. **The mean age was 60.9 (14.9) years and 67.5% were female. Comparison between pilot sites shows that the sites' samples significantly differed ($P < 0.001$) in all characteristics.** For example, participants in the Netherlands and France were younger than participants in Italy and the UK. About half of the UK sample was female, whereas the samples of the other sites included more females, up to 80% (Italy). The percentage of living alone ranged from 24.7% (UK) to 46.2% (France). Participants in Spain had the lowest level of education and lowest income, and participants in the Netherlands and Italy were most often not working. There is also variation in the type of participant: participants from France and the UK had often a chronic disease, while a substantial part of the participants from the other three sites were (also) caregiver.

Table 3a. Baseline characteristics of participants of the CDSMP intervention for all participants with baseline data, and according to pilot site

	Baseline group	Pilot site					P-value
	Total n=1825	NL n=388	Fr n=209	It n=324	Sp n=559	UK n=345	
Age, y	59.6±14.9	57.3±14.2	56.7±13.4	63.4±13.3	58.7±15.9	61.9±15.6	<.001*
Sex, female	1253(69.6)	296(77.1)	152(75.2)	259(80.4)	377(68.3)	169(49.6)	<.001†
Country of birth, other country	321(17.8)	94(24.5)	41(20.0)	28(8.8)	67(12.3)	91(26.5)	<.001†
Household composition							
Living alone	560(31.5)	156(40.9)	89(43.8)	92(29.3)	144(26.8)	79(22.9)	<.001†
Living with others	1219(68.5)	225(59.1)	114(56.2)	222(70.7)	393(73.2)	265(77.0)	
Educational level							
Primary or less	331(18.7)	17(4.6)	1(0.5)	17(5.3)	227(51.5)	19(5.5)	<.001†
Secondary	1062(59.9)	180(49.0)	186(91.6)	249(77.8)	195(36.2)	252(73.0)	
Tertiary or higher	380(21.4)	170(46.3)	16(7.9)	54(16.9)	66(12.3)	74(21.4)	
Income							
Less than categories below or no income	160(9.4)	13(3.6)	5(2.5)	14(4.5)	127(25.0)	1(0.3)	<.001†
Social welfare or disability pension	197(11.5)	47(13.2)	72(35.8)	5(1.6)	32(6.3)	41(12.2)	
Minimum pension to minimum wage	298(17.4)	41(11.5)	42(20.9)	23(7.5)	89(17.5)	103(30.7)	
Minimum wage to 1.5 times minimum wage	497(29.0)	74(20.7)	37(18.4)	183(59.4)	97(19.1)	106(31.5)	
≥1.5 times minimum wage	559(32.7)	182(51.0)	45(22.4)	83(26.9)	164(32.2)	85(25.3)	
Employment situation							
Employee or self-employed	1026(60.9)	167(46.8)	155(78.7)	146(45.6)	341(72.4)	217(64.0)	<.001†
Not working	658(39.1)	190(53.2)	42(21.3)	174(54.4)	130(27.6)	122(36.0)	
Type of participant							
Having a chronic condition	1218(73.5)	193(71.0)	176(84.6)	163(50.3)	364(67.9)	322(93.3)	<.001†
Caregiver	315(19.0)	52(19.1)	23(11.1)	92(28.4)	134(25.0)	14(4.1)	
Both caregiver and having a chronic condition	125(7.5)	27(9.9)	9(4.3)	69(21.3)	38(7.1)	9(2.6)	

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%).

Missing items: Age=34; Sex=24; Country of birth=26; Household composition=46; Educational level=52; Income=114; Employment situation=141; Type of participant=167

Abbreviations: Fr, France; It, Italy; NL, the Netherlands; Sp, Spain; SD, standard deviation; UK, the United Kingdom

* P-value based on ANOVA; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on Chi-square test; significant P-values in bold

Table 3b. Baseline characteristics of participants of the CDSMP intervention for all participants with both baseline and follow-up data, and according to pilot site

	Baseline + follow-up group	Pilot site					P-value
	Total n=1189	NL n=247	Fr n=124	It n=200	Sp n=343	UK n=275	
Age, y	60.9±14.93	58.4±13.3	59.2±12.1	62.2±12.9	61.4±15.1	62.6±15.8	0.004*
Sex, female	795(67.5)	187(76.0)	88(73.9)	160(80.4)	231(67.5)	129(47.4)	<.001†
Country of birth, other country	207(17.4)	55(22.4)	21(17.4)	16(8.0)	36(10.6)	79(28.7)	<.001†
Household composition							

Living alone	360(30.3)	96(39.5)	55(46.2)	54(27.7)	87(26.0)	68(24.7)	<.001†
Living with others	807(69.2)	147(60.5)	64(53.8)	141(72.3)	248(74.0)	207(75.3)	
Educational level							
Primary or less	195(16.7)	7(2.9)	1(0.8)	2(1.0)	168(50.3)	17(6.2)	<.001†
Secondary	709(60.9)	118(49.6)	109(90.8)	156(78.8)	124(37.1)	202(73.5)	
Tertiary or higher	261(22.4)	113(47.5)	10(8.3)	40(20.2)	42(12.6)	56(20.4)	
Income							
Less than categories below or no income	88(7.8)	10(4.3)	3(2.5)	6(3.1)	68(21.5)	1(0.4)	<.001†
Social welfare or disability pension	115(10.2)	29(12.4)	37(31.4)	2(1.0)	14(4.4)	33(12.1)	
Minimum pension to minimum wage	196(17.3)	23(9.9)	27(22.9)	12(6.2)	58(18.3)	76(27.9)	
Minimum wage to 1.5 times minimum wage	355(31.3)	52(22.3)	22(18.6)	118(61.1)	69(21.8)	94(34.6)	
≥1,5 times minimum wage	379(33.5)	119(51.1)	29(24.6)	55(28.5)	108(34.1)	68(25.0)	
Employment situation							
Employee or self-employed	676(60.8)	105(45.3)	90(78.9)	86(43.4)	217(73.3)	178(65.7)	<.001†
Not working	435(39.2)	127(54.7)	24(21.1)	112(56.6)	79(26.7)	93(34.3)	
Type of participant							
Having a chronic condition	819(73.6)	120(67.4)	105(84.7)	97(48.5)	238(70.8)	259(94.2)	<.001†
Caregiver	194(17.4)	39(21.9)	13(10.5)	57(28.5)	75(22.3)	10(3.6)	
Both caregiver and having a chronic condition	100(9.0)	19(10.7)	6(4.8)	46(23.0)	23(6.8)	6(2.2)	

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%).

Missing items: Age=7; Sex=11; Country of birth=8; Household composition=22; Educational level=24; Income=56; Employment situation=24; Type of participant=76

Abbreviations: Fr, France; It, Italy; NL, the Netherlands; Sp, Spain; UK, the United Kingdom

* P-value based on ANOVA; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on Chi-square test; significant P-values in bold

Objective 1 Self-management, healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, medication adherence and HR-QoL

What are the benefits of the CDSMP intervention for the target population in terms of self-management in healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, adherence to medications and Health-Related Quality of Life (HR-QoL)?

A description of the outcome measures of objective 1 at baseline (T0) is presented in **Table 4ab** for the total group and by pilot site. It shows significant differences in all outcome measures at baseline between the sites. For example, participants in Italy and Spain experienced a higher self-management than participants in the UK. Dutch participants performed most physical exercise; Italian and Spanish participants most often have breakfast. Most alcohol users were Dutch and British participants, while most smokers were France and Spanish participants. Depressive symptoms, sleep problems and fatigue were most common among France participants. HR-QoL measures varied per pilot site with lower self-rated overall health in France and British participants.

Table 4a. Baseline outcomes measures (objective 1) of participants of the CDSMP intervention for all participants with both baseline and follow-up data, and according to pilot site

	Baseline +	Pilot site					P-value
	follow-up group	NL	Fr	It	Sp	UK	
	Total						
	n=1189	n=247	n=124	n=200	n=343	n=275	
Self-management							
CDSE-6 (score range 1-10) §	6.70±2.15	6.71±1.76	6.04±1.98	7.28±1.83	7.58±2.15	5.73±2.21	<.001*
Lifestyle factors							
Physical exercise							
Stretching/strengthening (min/wk)	35.58±61.14	27.97±53.75	39.63±60.95	50.94±73.55	42.91±61.12	31.04 ±57.23	0.001*
Aerobic exercise (min/wk)	150.82±123.14	211.95±137.56	135.25±107.58	147.76±107.76	131.56±115.97	128.73±117.42	<.001*
Walk for exercise (min/wk)	95.25±66.78	106.96±64.67	88.09±67.92	103.43±69.32	90.79±64.84	87.75±67.01	0.002*
Swimming or aquatic exercise (min/wk)	8.40±30.47	8.70±30.55	5.14±16.81	12.30±39.67	5.53±23.45	10.29±34.75	0.120*
Bicycling (min/wk)	22.78±48.62	66.58±67.78	20.45±45.28	10.53±32.53	9.79±32.26	6.27±22.58	<.001*
Other aerobic exercise (min/wk)	30.24±61.89	36.37±61.69	28.77±61.47	30.70±65.00	31.02±67.12	24.44±54.08	0.302
Sedentary behaviour (week day) (min/wk)	5.99±3.31	7.57±3.04	5.99±3.49	6.15±3.06	4.11±2.62	6.71±3.30	<.001*
Sedentary behaviour (weekend day) (min/wk)	5.78±3.23	6.92±3.07	5.96±3.26	4.99±2.92	4.39±2.62	6.75±3.44	<.001*
Fruit, >1 portion/d	609(52.01)	125(50.61)	49(39.84)	143(72.96)	179(54.24)	113(41.09)	<.001†
Vegetables, >1 portion/d	438(37.69)	104(42.45)	42(34.15)	109(55.61)	82(25.15)	101(37.13)	<.001†
Having breakfast, >5 d/wk	918(80.46)	165(69.33)	80(67.80)	171(89.06)	305(95.31)	197(72.16)	<.001†
Alcohol, 2 times/wk or more	282(24.14)	84(34.01)	24(19.51)	45(22.96)	55(16.77)	74(27.01)	<.001†
Smoking, yes	157(13.69)	26(10.57)	27(23.48)	21(11.29)	71(21.65)	12(4.41)	<.001†
Depressive symptoms (PHQ-8 ≥10)	248(24.12)	43(18.53)	43(44.79)	27(15.61)	56(20.44)	79(31.23)	<.001†
Sleep problems (score range 0-10) ‡	4.41±3.02	4.39±2.94	5.56±2.94	4.02±2.87	3.38±2.91	5.44±2.87	<.001*
Fatigue (score range 0-10) ‡	4.77±3.04	5.09±2.83	6.26±2.64	4.34±2.73	3.41±3.12	5.71±2.84	<.001*
Medication adherence (SMAQ), no adherence	501(57.13)	91(63.63)	52(54.74)	82(58.99)	122(48.61)	154(61.85)	0.013†
HR-QoL							
PCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) §	43.7±11.3	46.82±9.96	37.86±10.61	49.33±8.79	44.45±11.14	38.69±11.53	<.001*
MCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) §	43.6±10.1	42.22±9.59	39.32±9.75	44.74±9.93	47.56±9.13	41.96±10.31	<.001*
EQ-5D-5L utility values#	0.69±0.26	0.85±0.18	0.56±0.32	0.82±0.14	0.55±0.22	0.69±0.30	<.001*
EQ-5D-5L Overall health (score range 0-100) §	67.81±21.47	72.20±17.20	56.21±21.22	72.94±19.51	72.27±20.74	60.27±23.14	<.001*

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

Abbreviations: CDSE-6, short 6-item Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument; HR-QoL, Health-related quality of life; PHQ-8, 8-item Patient Health Questionnaire; SMAQ, short 6-item Medication Adherence Questionnaire; MCS, Mental Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; PCS, Physical Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; SF-12, 12-item Short form

The values are from participants who have data on the outcome measure at both T0 and T1 (paired).

* P-value based on ANOVA; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on Chi-square test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

Range from less than 0 (where 0 is the value of a health state equivalent to dead; negative values representing values as worse than dead) to 1 (the value of full health), with higher scores indicating higher health utility.

Table 4b shows the outcome measures of objective 1 at baseline (T0) and follow-up (T1) of participants with both baseline and follow-up data, including the results of the paired T test. **Over a period of 6 months, participants of the CDSMP intervention experienced an increase in self-management (+0.29 pt). They also swam more often (+2.8 min/wk), were sitting less hours per day (week day: -0.34; weekend day: -0.34 min/wk), used less alcohol (-3.1%) and had less depressive symptoms (-3.7%). Moreover, their physical and mental HR-QoL significantly increased (respectively +1.0, +1.4 pt) as well as their health utility (+0.02 pt) and self-rated overall health (+ 2.74 pt); however, the increases on these HR-QoL scales were not large. For the other lifestyle factors, sleep, fatigue and medication adherence, no significant changes over time were observed.**

Table 4b. Self-management, healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, medication adherence and HR-QoL of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up (n=1189)

	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Self-management				
CDSE-6 (score range 1-10) [§]	1073	6.70±2.15	6.99±2.06	<.001*
Lifestyle factors				
Physical exercise				
Stretching/strengthening (min/wk)	1092	35.58±61.14	36.58±56.61	0.571*
Aerobic exercise (min/wk)	1173	150.82±123.14	153.57±126.44	0.427*
Walk for exercise (min/wk)	1143	95.25±66.78	92.82±66.87	0.229*
Swimming or aquatic exercise (min/wk)	1048	8.40±30.47	11.16±34.96	0.008*
Bicycling (min/wk)	1061	22.78±48.62	25.22±51.98	0.052*
Other aerobic exercise (min/wk)	1068	30.24±61.89	29.49±62.02	0.715*
Sedentary behaviour (week day) (min/wk)	1069	5.99±3.31	5.65±3.07	<.001*
Sedentary behaviour (weekend day) (min/wk)	1075	5.78±3.23	5.44±2.86	<.001*
Fruit, >1 portion/d	1171	609(52.01)	582(49.70)	0.109†
Vegetables, >1 portion/d	1162	438(37.69)	447(38.47)	0.633†
Having breakfast, >5 d/wk	1141	918(80.46)	920(80.63)	0.940†
Alcohol, 2 times/wk or more	1168	282(24.14)	246(21.06)	0.002‡
Smoking, yes	1147	157(13.69)	156(13.60)	1.000†
Depressive symptoms (PHQ-8 ≥10)	1028	248(24.12)	210(20.43)	0.007‡
Sleep problems (score range 0-10) [‡]	1161	4.41±3.02	4.44±3.06	0.760*
Fatigue (score range 0-10) [‡]	1150	4.77±3.04	4.67±2.98	0.160*
Medication adherence (SMAQ), no adherence	877	501(57.13)	479(54.62)	0.189†
HR-QoL				
PCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) [§]	1006	43.7±11.3	44.7±10.9	<.001*
MCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) [§]	1006	43.6±10.1	45.0±9.4	<.001*
EQ-5D-5L utility values [#]	1147	0.69±0.26	0.71±0.26	0.002*
EQ-5D-5L Overall health (score range 0-100) [§]	1136	67.81±21.47	70.55±20.25	<.001*

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

Range from less than 0 (where 0 is the value of a health state equivalent to dead; negative values representing values as worse than dead) to 1 (the value of full health), with higher scores indicating higher health utility.

Abbreviations: CDSE-6, short 6-item Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument; HR-QoL, Health-related quality of life; PHQ-8, 8-item Patient Health Questionnaire; SMAQ, short 6-item Medication Adherence Questionnaire; MCS, Mental

Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; PCS, Physical Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; SF-12, 12-item Short form

Stratified analyses

To get more insight into the effects of the CDSMP intervention on the outcome measures, several stratified analyses were performed: by sex, age, pilot site and COVID-19 outbreak. The findings for men and women are shown in **Table 4c**. **It shows that the effects of the CDSMP intervention on sedentary behaviour, alcohol use and depressive symptoms were more pronounced in women compared with men.**

Table 4c. Self-management, healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, medication adherence and HR-QoL of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up, according to sex (n=1189)

	Men				Women			
	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Self-management								
CDSE-6 (score range 1-10) §	354	6.57±2.23	7.03±2.04	<.001*	712	6.77±2.10	6.97±2.07	0.007*
Lifestyle factors								
Physical exercise								
Stretching/strengthening (min/wk)	365	45.37±67.56	40.93±58.96	0.117*	718	33.95±57.57	34.20±55.12	0.911*
Aerobic exercise (min/wk)	381	158.46±127.09	164.96±139.76	0.304*	782	147.51±121.59	148.75±119.32	0.765*
Walk for exercise (min/wk)	375	97.28±65.66	94.12±69.20	0.367*	759	94.21±67.31	92.47±65.80	0.484*
Swimming or aquatic exercise (min/wk)	349	7.48±30.42	10.70±36.17	0.069*	690	8.91±30.66	11.54±34.56	0.042*
Bicycling (min/wk)	353	22.27±47.81	23.67±50.98	0.527*	698	23.17±49.21	26.02±52.47	0.062*
Other aerobic exercise (min/wk)	360	34.58±67.63	41.50±75.41	0.061*	699	28.22±58.89	23.54±53.24	0.057*
Sedentary behaviour (week day) (min/wk)	349	6.30±3.29	6.11±3.13	0.242*	710	5.85±3.32	5.43±3.03	<.001*
Sedentary behaviour (weekend day) (min/wk)	351	6.14±3.26	5.87±3.06	0.117*	714	5.62±3.21	5.24±2.75	0.001*
Fruit, >1 portion/d	378	158(41.80)	146(38.62)	0.257†	782	446(57.03)	431(55.12)	0.282†
Vegetables, >1 portion/d	375	116(30.93)	118(31.47)	0.915†	776	319(41.11)	326(42.01)	0.664†
Having breakfast, >5 d/wk	370	288(77.84)	294(79.46)	0.504†	761	622(81.73)	619(81.34)	0.853†
Alcohol, 2 times/wk or more	378	122(32.28)	109(28.84)	0.086†	779	157(20.15)	134(17.20)	0.012†
Smoking, yes	375	63(16.80)	60(16.00)	0.607†	762	91(11.94)	93(12.20)	0.839†
Depressive symptoms (PHQ-8 ≥10)	341	72(21.11)	76(22.29)	0.699†	682	175(25.66)	134(19.65)	<.001†
Sleep problems (score range 0-10) ‡	373	4.08±3.03	4.20±3.00	0.369*	777	4.59±3.00	4.56±3.09	0.793*
Fatigue (score range 0-10) ‡	372	4.38±3.10	4.24±2.91	0.278*	767	4.98±3.01	4.87±3.00	0.259*
Medication adherence (SMAQ), no adherence	309	173(55.99)	160(51.78)	0.232†	562	325(57.83)	314(55.87)	0.419†
HR-QoL								
PCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) §	324	43.18±11.55	44.38±11.00	0.006*	675	43.87±11.22	44.76±10.95	0.003*
MCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) §	324	44.53±10.00	45.68±9.10	0.019*	675	43.15±10.06	44.68±9.59	<.001*
EQ-5D-5L utility values#	370	0.69±0.26	0.70±0.26	0.441*	767	0.70±0.26	0.72±0.26	<.001*
EQ-5D-5L Overall health (score range 0-100) §	365	67.80±20.80	71.22±19.41	<.001*	761	67.76±21.79	70.22±20.68	0.001*

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

Range from less than 0 (where 0 is the value of a health state equivalent to dead; negative values representing values as worse than dead) to 1 (the value of full health), with higher scores indicating higher health utility.

Abbreviations: CDSE-6, short 6-item Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument; HR-QoL, Health-related quality of life; PHQ-8, 8-item Patient Health Questionnaire; SMAQ, short 6-item Medication Adherence Questionnaire; MCS, Mental Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; PCS, Physical Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; SF-12, 12-item Short form

The findings by age (younger/older than 65 years) are presented in Table 4d. **The significant effects of the CDSMP intervention found in the total sample remained only significant in younger participants but not in older participants, except for alcohol use. A significant decrease in fatigue was observed in younger participants.**

Table 4d. Self-management, healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, medication adherence and HR-QoL of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up, according to age (n=1189)

	<65 years				≥65 years			
	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Self-management								
CDSE-6 (score range 1-10) §	625	6.63±2.13	7.01±2.03	<.001*	442	6.81±2.17	6.96±2.10	0.128*
Lifestyle factors								
Physical exercise								
Stretching/strengthening (min/wk)	650	38.35±63.73	38.95±59.88	0.793*	718	33.95±57.57	34.20±55.12	0.241*
Aerobic exercise (min/wk)	677	157.82±134.49	164.36±136.29	0.173*	489	142.85±104.95	140.25±110.15	0.601*
Walk for exercise (min/wk)	664	93.07±67.96	91.76±67.42	0.623*	472	99.31±64.94	95.24±66.13	0.193*
Swimming or aquatic exercise (min/wk)	631	8.65±32.62	11.24±35.76	0.052*	411	8.10±27.10	11.17±33.98	0.067*
Bicycling (min/wk)	637	27.01±53.60	28.92±55.71	0.255*	418	16.65±39.45	19.95±45.58	0.088*
Other aerobic exercise (min/wk)	644	33.12±66.52	34.12±68.45	0.720*	418	26.23±54.20	22.64±50.29	0.223*
Sedentary behaviour (week day) (min/wk)	622	6.32±3.41	5.88±3.26	<.001*	441	5.52±3.09	5.31±2.76	0.098*
Sedentary behaviour (weekend day) (min/wk)	623	5.92±3.41	5.47±2.96	<.001*	446	5.56±2.95	5.38±2.71	0.190*
Fruit, >1 portion/d	677	314(46.38)	301(44.46)	0.312†	487	292(59.96)	279(57.29)	0.275†
Vegetables, >1 portion/d	672	260(38.69)	261(38.84)	1.000†	484	178(36.78)	185(38.22)	0.576†
Having breakfast, >5 d/wk	658	506(76.90)	501(76.14)	0.709†	476	408(85.71)	415(87.18)	0.435†
Alcohol, 2 times/wk or more	674	141(20.92)	123(18.25)	0.048†	487	140(28.75)	123(25.26)	0.031†
Smoking, yes	667	142(21.29)	145(21.74)	0.719†	473	15(3.17)	11(2.33)	0.289†
Depressive symptoms (PHQ-8 ≥10)	608	186(30.59)	142(23.36)	<.001†	414	60(14.49)	67(16.18)	0.418†
Sleep problems (score range 0-10) ‡	667	4.51±3.10	4.43±3.09	0.466*	487	4.27±2.91	4.44±3.03	0.163*
Fatigue (score range 0-10) ‡	665	5.02±3.12	4.72±3.03	0.002*	478	4.41±2.91	4.58±2.93	0.147*
Medication adherence (SMAQ), no adherence	443	285(64.33)	271(61.17)	0.243†	428	210(49.07)	202(47.20)	0.542†
HR-QoL								
PCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) §	590	45.21±11.40	46.33±10.98	<.001*	412	41.51±10.94	42.25±10.48	0.064*

MCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) [§]	590	41.84±10.06	44.14±9.42	<.001*	412	46.21±9.51	46.33±9.27	0.770*
EQ-5D-5L utility values [#]	664	0.70±0.26	0.73±0.24	<.001*	476	0.69±0.26	0.68±0.27	0.419*
EQ-5D-5L Overall health (score range 0-100) [§]	667	67.33±12.34	71.08±20.69	<.001*	462	68.80±20.01	69.86±19.54	0.216*

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

Range from less than 0 (where 0 is the value of a health state equivalent to dead; negative values representing values as worse than dead) to 1 (the value of full health), with higher scores indicating higher health utility.

Abbreviations: CDSE-6, short 6-item Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument; HR-QoL, Health-related quality of life; PHQ-8, 8-item Patient Health Questionnaire; SMAQ, short 6-item Medication Adherence Questionnaire; MCS, Mental Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; PCS, Physical Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; SF-12, 12-item Short form

In **Supplemental Table 4e to 4i of Annex 3**, the results of objective 1 are shown for each pilot site. These exploratory analyses show that the estimated effects of the CDSMP intervention varied between the sites. However, it should be noted that the sample sizes of each pilot site are smaller. Therefore, the estimations may be less precise, and the significance of the findings should be interpreted with caution.

In **Supplemental Table 4j of Annex 4**, the results of objective 1 are shown stratified by participants filling in the follow-up questionnaire before or after the COVID-19 outbreak. In participants of after the outbreak, the effects of the CDSMP intervention remained only significant for some outcome measures (i.e. aerobic exercise and vegetable intake), while in participants of before the outbreak, other outcome measures remained only significant (i.e. swimming, sedentary behaviour, alcohol use and health utility). So, the significance of the effects mostly differed per outcome measure; however, the smaller number of participants of after the outbreak (less power) might have influenced these differences in effects.

Objective 2 Health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors

What are the effects of the CDSMP intervention for the target population on health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and the prevalence of experienced medical errors?

A description of the outcome measures of objective 2 at baseline (T0) are presented for each pilot site in **Table 5a**. For most outcome measures at baseline, there are differences between the sites. For example, France participants reported the highest health literacy, whereas Dutch and British participants reported best communication with healthcare providers. Italian participants experienced least medical errors.

Table 5a. Baseline outcomes measures (objective 2) of participants of the CDSMP intervention for all participants with both baseline and follow-up data, and according to pilot site

	Baseline + follow-up group Total n=1189	Pilot site					P-value
		NL n=247	Fr n=124	It n=200	Sp n=343	UK n=275	
Health literacy (HLQ)							
Ability to find good health information (score range 1-5) [‡]	1.93±0.81	1.86±0.67	2.37±0.96	1.80±0.73	1.81±0.73	1.95±0.83	<.001*

Understand health information well enough to know what to do (score range 1-5) ‡	1.94±0.77	2.01±0.68	2.21±0.81	1.67±0.69	1.84±0.71	2.05±0.82	<.001*
Communication with healthcare providers (score range 0-5) §	2.05±1.24	2.44±1.17	1.97±1.18	2.09±1.22	1.78±1.29	2.25±1.32	<.001*
Prevalence of experienced medical errors							
Your healthcare provider did not explain this in a way you understood, % yes	324(33.30)	26(31.10)	34(29.06)	59(32.24)	92(28.84)	113(41.39)	0.017†
Personally experienced a medical error in your own care, % yes	245(26.98)	24(29.27)	34(30.36)	45(25.00)	75(28.74)	67(24.54)	0.652†
The medical error is a minor/major problem for you, % yes	122(85.31)	8(80.00)	23(95.83)	20(76.92)	32(80.00)	39(90.70)	0.222†

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

Abbreviations: HLQ, Health literacy questionnaire

The values are from participants who have data on the outcome measure at both T0 and T1 (paired).

* P-value based on ANOVA; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on Chi-square test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

High number of missing data on this question because this is a sub-question (only for those who experienced an error)

Table 5b shows the outcome measures of objective 2 at baseline (T0) and follow-up (T1), including the results of the paired T test or McNemar test. **Over a period of 6 months, participants of the CDSMP intervention reported that their communication with healthcare providers significantly improved (+0.17 pt). Moreover, they misunderstood their healthcare provider less often (-4.2%) and experienced fewer medical errors (-8.3%). Besides, their health literacy was increased after 6 months; this increase was significant for the item understanding health information to know what to do (-0.10 pt) and borderline significant for the item ability to find good health information (-0.06 pt).**

Table 5b. Health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up (n=1189)

	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Health literacy (HLQ)				
Ability to find good health information (score range 1-5) ‡	721	1.93±0.81	1.87±0.74	0.060*
Understand health information well enough to know what to do (score range 1-5) ‡	737	1.94±0.77	1.84±0.73	0.001*
Communication with healthcare providers (score range 0-5) §	962	2.05±1.24	2.22±1.31	<.001*
Prevalence of experienced medical errors				
Your healthcare provider did not explain this in a way you understood, % yes	973	324(33.30)	283(29.09)	0.017†
Personally experienced a medical error in your own care, % yes	908	245(26.98)	170(18.72)	<.001†
The medical error is a minor/major problem for you, % yes	143#	122(85.31)	115(80.42)	0.248†

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

Abbreviations: HLQ, Health literacy questionnaire

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

High number of missing data on this question because this is a sub-question (only for those who experienced an error)

Stratified analyses

To get more insight into the effects of the CDSMP intervention on health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors, several stratified analyses were performed: by sex, age, pilot site and COVID-19 outbreak.

The findings for men and women separately are shown in Table 5c. **The significant effects on health literacy, communication with healthcare provider and understanding their healthcare provider were mainly found in women but not in men.**

Table 5c. Health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up, according to sex (n=1189)

	Men				Women			
	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Health literacy (HLQ)								
Ability to find good health information (score range 1-5) ‡	248	1.88±0.79	1.83±0.68	0.189*	467	1.96±0.82	1.91±0.77	0.003*
Understand health information well enough to know what to do (score range 1-5) ‡	261	1.88±0.73	1.82±0.67	0.254*	470	1.97±0.79	1.86±0.76	0.254*
Communication with healthcare providers (score range 0-5) §	326	2.04±1.27	2.15±1.27	0.090*	627	2.06±1.22	2.26±1.33	<.001*
Prevalence of experienced medical errors								
Your healthcare provider did not explain this in a way you understood, % yes	333	114(34.23)	103(30.93)	0.305†	632	208(32.91)	179(28.32)	0.038†
Personally experienced a medical error in your own care, % yes	323	81(25.08)	64(19.81)	0.044†	577	163(28.25)	104(18.02)	<.001†
The medical error is a minor/major problem for you, % yes	54#	48(88.89)	43(79.63)	0.180†	88#	73(82.95)	71(80.68)	0.815†

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

Abbreviations: HLQ, Health literacy questionnaire

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

High number of missing data on this question because this is a sub-question (only for those who experienced an error)

The findings by age (younger/older than 65 years) are presented in Table 5d. The effect of the CDSMP intervention on understanding health information was only significant in younger participants, while the effect on understanding your healthcare provider remained only significant in older participants. The improvements in communication with healthcare providers and medical errors were significant in both age groups.

Table 5d. Health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up, according to age (n=1189)

	<65 years				≥65 years			
	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Health literacy (HLQ)								
Ability to find good health information (score range 1-5) ‡	403	1.96±0.86	1.89±0.76	0.094*	314	1.89±0.74	1.85±0.71	0.361*
Understand health information well enough to know what to do (score range 1-5) ‡	400	1.98±0.80	1.83±0.76	0.001*	333	1.89±0.73	1.83±0.69	0.236*
Communication with healthcare providers (score range 0-5) §	535	2.02±1.24	2.24±1.32	<.001*	421	2.07±1.24	2.19±1.29	0.039*
Prevalence of experienced medical errors								
Your healthcare provider did not explain this in a way you understood, % yes	538	192(35.69)	178(33.09)	0.301†	429	132(30.77)	105(24.48)	0.018†
Personally experienced a medical error in your own care, % yes	512	164(32.03)	112(21.88)	<.001†	390	80(20.51)	56(14.36)	0.008†
The medical error is a minor/major problem for you, % yes	98	89(90.82)	83(84.69)	0.263†	44	33(75.00)	32(72.37)	1.000†

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

Abbreviations: HLQ, Health literacy questionnaire

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

High number of missing data on this question because this is a sub-question (only for those who experienced an error)

In **Supplemental Table 5e to 5i of Annex 5**, the exploratory results of objective 2 are shown for each pilot site. Due to the smaller sample size for each pilot site, the significance of the findings should be interpreted with caution.

In **Supplemental Table 5j of Annex 6**, the results of objective 2 are shown stratified by filling in the follow-up questionnaire before or after the COVID-19 outbreak. It shows that some effects were observed both before and after the COVID-19 outbreak (improvement in communication with healthcare provider and fewer medical errors experienced). We found a borderline significant improvement in the understanding of healthcare provider only in participants who filled in the follow-up questionnaire after the outbreak, whereas an improvement in the understanding of health information remained significant only in participants of before the outbreak. This indicates that the pandemic did not consistently affect the effects on health literacy and experience of medical errors. The smaller number of participants of after the outbreak (less power) might have influenced these inconsistent effects.

Objective 3 Societal cost savings

What are the societal cost savings of the CDSMP intervention in terms of reducing healthcare utilization and productivity losses among the target population?

Using the baseline measurement as control group, a preliminary cost-effectiveness analysis was performed with a time horizon of 6 months and from 1) the healthcare perspective and 2) the societal perspective. Analyses from both perspectives are described below.

The healthcare perspective

The healthcare perspective only takes the healthcare costs into consideration. Healthcare costs for individual participants were determined by *multiplying* resource use (doctor appointments, hospital emergency room visits and hospitalised nights) with corresponding unit prices for 2017. Resource use was collected using 3 items from the SMRC Health Care Utilization questionnaire regarding the number of doctor appointments (GP or specialist), number of hospital emergency room visits and number of hospitalised nights in the past 6 months (see items E1 to E4 in the baseline questionnaire Annex 1; items F1 to F4 in the follow-up questionnaire Annex 2).

Table 6 shows the resource use at baseline (T0) and follow-up (T1) of participants with both baseline and follow-up data, including the results of the paired T test or McNemar test. **The mean number of doctor appointments, emergency room visits and nights during overnight hospital stays all significantly decreased after 6 months (respectively -1.18, -0.18 and -0.35 visits/nights).**

Table 6. Resource use of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline (T0) and at 6-months follow-up (T1) (n=1189)

	n (paired)	T0	T1	P-value*
Doctor appointments	1120	4.35±5.98	3.17±4.52	<0.001
Hospital emergency room visits	1139	0.42±2.07	0.24±0.77	0.002
Hospitalised nights	1111	0.83±4.12	0.48±2.77	0.005

Note: Presented as mean±SD

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

To estimate healthcare costs unit prices of the three resources are needed. Calculation of the unit prices in the five countries are shown in Table 7a. These unit prices were based on 2014 Dutch unit prices taken from the Dutch Manual for Costing in economic evaluations [31]. The Dutch unit prices were inflated to 2017 using the Eurostat Harmonised Indices of Consumer Prices (HICP; <https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/nl/dataset/83133NED/table?ts=1589291456239>) and adjusted using the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Purchasing Power Parities (PPPs) for actual individual consumption (<https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=CPL#>) to reflect French, Italian, Spanish and British 2017 unit prices. As British PPPs are expressed in British pounds, historical exchange rates were used to convert British pounds to euros (<https://www.xe.com/currencytables/?from=GBP&date=2017-07-01>). Table 7b shows the calculated unit prices used for the valuation of the resource use in the five pilot sites.

Table 7a. Calculation of unit prices for each country

	the Netherlands		France	Italy	Spain	United Kingdom
	2014 Dutch unit prices (euro)*	Inflated to 2017 (euro)**	Adjusted to France	Adjusted to Italy	Adjusted to Spain	Adjusted to the United Kingdom****
OECD PPPs***		0.823	0.774	0.732	0.671	0.747
Doctor appointments	91	92	92*0.774 /0.823	92*0.732 /0.823	92*0.671 /0.823	92*0.747*1.14 /0.823
Hospital emergency room visits	259	263	263*0.774 /0.823	263*0.732 /0.823	263*0.671 /0.823	263*0.747*1.14 /0.823
Hospitalised nights	476	484	484*0.774 /0.823	484*0.732 /0.823	484*0.671 /0.823	484*0.747*1.14 /0.823

* ref: <https://www.zorginstituutnederland.nl/publicaties/publicatie/2016/02/29/richtlijn-voor-het-uitvoeren-van-economische-evaluaties-in-de-gezondheidszorg> → 'Richtlijn voor het uitvoeren van economische evaluaties in de gezondheidszorg (verdiepingsmodules)' page 39 (hospital admission days), page 41 (doctor appointments) and page 42 (emergency room visits).

** using the Eurostat Harmonised Indices of Consumer Prices (HICP; ref: <https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/nl/dataset/83133NED/table?ts=1589291456239>) → Filter 'Perioden' = 'jaren' and see 2015=0.2, 2016=0.1 and 2017=1.3. Calculation: $91 * 1.002 * 1.001 * 1.013 = 92$

*** using the OECD PPPs for actual individual consumption (ref: <https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=CPL#>) → PPPs and exchange rates → PPPs for actual individual consumption → year 2017

**** British pounds converted to euros (rate: 1.140); ref: <https://www.xe.com/currencytables/?from=GBP&date=2017-07-01>

Table 7b. Unit prices used for the valuation of resource use of each country (for 2017; in euros)

	the Netherlands	France	Italy	Spain	United Kingdom
OECD PPPs	0.823	0.774	0.732	0.671	0.852*
Doctor appointments	92	87	82	75	95
Hospital emergency room visits	263	247	234	214	272
Hospitalised nights	484	455	430	395	501

* British pounds converted to euros (rate: 1.140); ref: <https://www.xe.com/currencytables/?from=GBP&date=2017-07-01>

The following tables show the mean use of the three resources per participant at baseline and follow-up for each pilot site. With the means, the healthcare costs per participant at baseline and follow-up are calculated as well as the change in healthcare costs over 6 months for each pilot site (Table 8a-8e). For example, participants from the Netherlands (Table 8a) reported a mean number of doctor appointments of 4.51 at baseline. When multiplied by the unit price (92 euro), the mean costs are 415 euro. After 6 months, the costs are 254 euro, resulting in a decrease of 160 euro. When combining the changes in doctor appointments, emergency room visits and hospitalised nights, the total decrease is 352 euro per participant. All changes in resource use in each

site were decreases, except for doctor appointments in France, which increased with 0.58 visits. Still, total healthcare cost savings for France are estimated to be 254 euro (Table 8b). Italy has the largest decrease in costs (452 euro), mainly due to a mean decrease of 0.87 hospitalised nights (Table 8c). The smallest cost savings are estimated for Spain (179 euro; Table 8d), and UK's savings (344 euro; Table 8e) are comparable to those of the Netherlands.

Table 8a. Netherlands - healthcare costs per participant at baseline (T0) and at 6-months follow-up (T1)

	n (paired)	T0			T1			Δ Healthcare costs (euro)
		Mean resource use (number of units)	Unit price (euro)	Mean healthcare costs (euro)	Mean resource use (number of units)	Unit price (euro)	Mean healthcare costs (euro)	
Doctor appointments	238	4.51	92	415	2.76	92	254.4	-160
Hospital emergency room visits	243	0.12	263	31	0.07	263	19.5	-12
Hospitalised nights	237	0.52	484	251	0.15	484	71.5	-180
				697			345	-352

Table 8b. France - healthcare costs per participant at baseline (T0) and at 6-months follow-up (T1)

	n (paired)	T0			T1			Δ Healthcare costs (euro)
		Mean resource use (number of units)	Unit price (euro)	Mean healthcare costs (euro)	Mean resource use (number of units)	Unit price (euro)	Mean healthcare costs (euro)	
Doctor appointments	116	5.45	87	471	6.03	87	521.4	50
Hospital emergency room visits	122	0.35	247	87	0.13	247	32.4	-55
Hospitalised nights	115	1.01	455	459	0.46	455	209.8	-249
				1018			764	-254

Table 8c. Italy - healthcare costs per participant at baseline (T0) and at 6-months follow-up (T1)

	n (paired)	T0			T1			Δ Healthcare costs (euro)
		Mean resource use (number of units)	Unit price (euro)	Mean healthcare costs (euro)	Mean resource use (number of units)	Unit price (euro)	Mean healthcare costs (euro)	
Doctor appointments	186	3.64	82	298	2.72	82	222.2	-76
Hospital emergency room visits	182	0.15	234	36	0.14	234	32.1	-4
Hospitalised nights	177	1.32	430	567	0.45	430	194.6	-372
				901			449	-452

Table 8d. Spain - healthcare costs per participant at baseline (T0) and at 6-months follow-up (T1)

	n (paired)	T0		T1		Δ Healthcare costs (euro)
		Mean resource use (number of units)	Unit price (euro)	Mean resource use (number of units)	Unit price (euro)	
Doctor appointments	307	3.84	75	2.74	75	-82
Hospital emergency room visits	319	0.61	214	0.40	214	-44
Hospitalised nights	313	0.88	395	0.74	395	-53
			764		585	-179

Table 8e. United Kingdom - healthcare costs per participant at baseline (T0) and at 6-months follow-up (T1)

	n (paired)	T0		T1		Δ Healthcare costs
		Mean resource use (number of units)	Unit price (euro)	Mean resource use (number of units)	Unit price (euro)	
Doctor appointments	273	4.80	95	3.12	95	-160
Hospital emergency room visits	273	0.67	272	0.30	272	-99
Hospitalised nights	269	0.66	501	0.49	501	-86
			968		624	-344

Health utility values obtained by the EQ-5D-5L instrument at baseline and follow-up are presented in Table 9 (see items B3 to B7 in the baseline questionnaire Annex 1). The change in health utility was largest in participants of France (increase of 0.072), while Spain had a little, non-significant decrease (0.011). Participants of Italy and the UK had a small increase, while Dutch participants' scores were stable. **For all sites together, a small increase in utility score was observed (0.016).**

The change in the EQ-5D-5L score was over a period of 6 months, so when by multiplying the change in EQ-5D-5L by the time in years (i.e. 6 months = 0.5 year), one obtains the change in utility in QALYs.

Table 9. Utility scores (EQ-5D-5L) of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline (T0) and at 6-months follow-up (T1) each pilot site and for the total sample (n=1189)

	T0	T1	Δ Utility score
the Netherlands	0.848	0.844	-0.004*
France	0.562	0.634	0.072
Italy	0.825	0.854	0.029
Spain	0.553	0.542	-0.011*
United Kingdom	0.688	0.718	0.030
Total	0.695	0.711	0.016

* The change is not statistically significant (P >0.05)

Table 10 shows the preliminary cost-effectiveness analysis from the healthcare perspective. **The mean saving of healthcare costs is 307 euro per participant for the total sample.** We applied a parameter analogous to the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER), which is defined as the ratio of the change in costs of an intervention to the change in effects of the intervention. Our 'ICER' is defined as the ratio of the change in healthcare costs (Table 8a-8e) to the change in health utility (Table 9). This ratio

ranges from a saving of 15,359 euro per 1-unit increase in utility score for Spain to a cost of 87,200 euro for the Netherlands. It should be noted that the decrease in the utility score in the Netherlands and Spain was however statistically not significant. **The weighted average of the five pilot sites is a saving of 19,832 euro per 1-unit increase in utility score.**

Table 10. Cost-effectiveness analysis with a time horizon of 6 months from the healthcare perspective for each for each pilot site and the weighted average of the total sample (n=1189)

	n	n _{weight}	Δ Healthcare costs (euro)	Δ Utility score	'ICER' (Δ Healthcare costs / Δ Utility score)
the Netherlands	247	0.21	-352	-0.004*	87200
France	124	0.10	-254	0.072	-3523
Italy	200	0.17	-452	0.029	-15359
Spain	343	0.29	-179	-0.011*	16278
United Kingdom	275	0.23	-344	0.030	-11355
Total*	1189	1	-307†	0.0155†	-19832

Abbreviations: ICER=incremental cost-effectiveness ratio

* The change is not statistically significant ($P>0.05$)

† Weighted n-average of the five countries

The societal perspective

In addition to the healthcare costs, the societal perspective takes productivity losses into account. Productivity losses for individual participants comprise of 1) lost productivity at paid work due to absenteeism and 2) lost productivity at unpaid work.

Lost productivity at *paid* work due to absenteeism was determined by multiplying the number of hours absent from work due to illness in the past 4 weeks with corresponding hourly productivity costs for 2017. The number of hours absent from work was collected using 3 items from the PCQ (see items H12 to H14 in the baseline questionnaire Annex 1).

Lost productivity at *unpaid* work was determined by multiplying the number of hours required to take over the unpaid work unable to do due to physical or psychological problems in the past 4 weeks with corresponding hourly shadow prices for 2017. The number of hours required to take over the unpaid work was collected using 3 items from the PCQ questionnaire (see items F3 to F5 in the baseline questionnaire Annex 1).

To estimate societal costs, hourly productivity costs and hourly shadow prices are needed. Calculation of these hourly costs and prices in the five countries is shown in Table 11a. Hourly productivity costs and hourly shadow prices were based on 2014 Dutch unit prices taken from the Dutch Manual for Costing in economic evaluations [31]. The Dutch unit prices were inflated to 2017 using the Eurostat Harmonised Indices of Consumer Prices (HICP; <https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/nl/dataset/83133NED/table?ts=1589291456239>) and adjusted using the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Purchasing Power Parities (PPPs) for actual individual consumption (<https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=CPL#>) to reflect French, Italian, Spanish and British 2017 unit prices. As British PPPs are expressed in British pounds, historical exchange rates were used to convert British pounds to euros (<https://www.xe.com/currencytables/?from=GBP&date=2017-07-01>). Table 11b shows the calculated hourly productivity costs and hourly shadow prices used for the valuation of the productivity losses in the five pilot sites.

Table 11a. Calculation of hourly productivity costs and hourly shadow prices for each country

	the Netherlands		France	Italy	Spain	United Kingdom
	2014 Dutch unit prices (euro)*	Inflated to 2017 (euro)**	Adjusted to France	Adjusted to Italy	Adjusted to Spain	Adjusted to the United Kingdom****
OECD PPPs***		0.823	0.774	0.732	0.671	0.747
Hourly productivity costs						
Men	37.90	38.51	38.51*0.774 /0.823	38.51*0.732 /0.823	38.51*0.671 /0.823	38.51*0.747*1.14 /0.823
Women	31.60	32.11	32.11*0.774 /0.823	32.11*0.732 /0.823	32.11*0.671 /0.823	32.11*0.747*1.14 /0.823
Hourly shadow prices	14.00	14.22	14.22*0.774 /0.823	14.22*0.732 /0.823	14.22*0.671 /0.823	14.22*0.747*1.14 /0.823

* ref: <https://www.zorginstituutnederland.nl/publicaties/publicatie/2016/02/29/richtlijn-voor-het-uitvoeren-van-economische-evaluaties-in-de-gezondheidszorg> à 'Richtlijn voor het uitvoeren van economische evaluaties in de gezondheidszorg (verdiepingsmodules)' page 62 (Hourly productivity costs) and 63 (Hourly shadow prices).

** using the Eurostat Harmonised Indices of Consumer Prices (HICP; ref:

<https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/nl/dataset/83133NED/table?ts=1589291456239> → Filter 'Perioden' = 'jaren' and see 2015=0.2, 2016=0.1 and 2017=1.3. Calculation: 37.90*1.002*1.001*1.013=38.51

*** using the OECD PPPs for actual individual consumption (ref: <https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=CPL#>) → PPPs and exchange rates → PPPs for actual individual consumption → year 2017

**** British pounds converted to euros (rate: 1.140); ref: <https://www.xe.com/currencytables/?from=GBP&date=2017-07-01>

Table 11b. Hourly productivity costs and hourly shadow prices used for the valuation of productivity losses of each country (for 2017; in euros)

	the Netherlands		France	Italy	Spain	United Kingdom
OECD PPPs		0.823	0.774	0.732	0.671	0.852*
Hourly productivity costs						
Men	37.90	38.51	36.22	34.25	31.40	39.85
Women	31.60	32.11	30.20	28.56	26.18	33.23
Hourly shadow prices	14.00	14.22	13.37	12.65	11.59	14.71

* British pounds converted to euros (rate: 1.140); ref: <https://www.xe.com/currencytables/?from=GBP&date=2017-07-01>

Table 12 presents the mean productivity costs due to illness during 6 months per participant for both paid work and unpaid work at baseline and follow-up for each pilot site. The change in productivity costs over the 6 months (T1-T0) is also presented, indicating savings (negative changes) or costs (positive changes). The 6-month productivity costs per participant are retrieved using the country- (and sex-) specific hourly productivity costs and hourly shadow prices (Table 11b), and the reported absence from work and reported hours of inability to perform unpaid work/tasks during the last 4 weeks (extrapolated to 26 weeks = 6 months).

The decrease in productivity costs from paid work are largest in the UK (-983 euro), followed by the Netherlands (-152 euro) and Spain (-64 euro). In France and Italy, the costs increase by respectively 503 euro and 113 euro. **For the five countries together, the weighted average shows a decrease in productivity costs (=savings) of 206 euro per participant.**

Productivity costs from unpaid work are negative (=savings) in all pilot sites, ranging from -93 (Spain) to -633 (UK) euro per participant. **The weighted average shows a decrease in productivity costs (=savings) of 267 euro per participant.**

Note that these results should be interpreted with caution because of the (very) small numbers of participants reporting absence from work (T0: n=55; T1: n=43 of the 1189) or inability to perform unpaid work (T0: n=218; T1: n=193 of the 1189).

Table 12. Six-month productivity costs due to illness per participant at baseline (T0) and at 6-months follow-up (T1), for each pilot site and the weighted average of the total sample (n=1189)

	n	n weight	T0	T1	Δ Productivity costs (euro)
			Mean productivity costs per participant (euro)	Mean productivity costs per participant (euro)	
Paid work					
the Netherlands	247	0.21	904	752	-152
France	124	0.10	401	904	503
Italy	200	0.17	292	405	113
Spain	343	0.29	277	212	-64
United Kingdom	275	0.23	1251	269	-983
Total*	1189	1	648*	442*	-206
Unpaid work					
the Netherlands	247	0.21	1339	1144	-194
France	124	0.10	797	658	-139
Italy	200	0.17	610	379	-231
Spain	343	0.29	568	475	-93
United Kingdom	275	0.23	902	269	-633
Total*	1189	1	836*	569*	-267

*Weighted n-average of the five countries

In Table 13, the preliminary cost-effectiveness analysis from the societal perspective is shown. The change in societal costs, i.e. the sum of the change in healthcare costs (Table 8a-8e) and the change in productivity costs (Table 12), is negative (=saving) for four pilot sites, except for France (+110 euro). The latter is due to the productivity costs for France (+503 euro for paid work and -139 euro for unpaid work, see Table 12). However, these values on productivity costs should be interpreted with caution because of the low number of participants who reported to have been absent from paid work: in total 55 at baseline and 43 at follow-up (for France: 5 and 4, respectively). The number of participants who answered the questions regarding unpaid work were somewhat higher (218 at baseline and 193 at follow-up). So, the findings regarding the societal perspective should be interpreted cautiously in France separately. **For the five sites together, which is the significant result, the weighted average is a saving of 780 euro per participant.**

Together with the change in utility (Table 9), the 'ICER' is calculated. This ratio ranges from a saving of 64,677 euro per 1-unit increase in utility score for the UK to a cost of 172,880 euro for the Netherlands. **The weighted average of the five pilot sites is a saving of 50,397 euro per 1-unit increase in utility score.**

As mentioned for the productivity costs (Table 12), which are used for the societal costs in Table 13, note that these results should be interpreted with caution because of the small numbers of participants reporting absence from work or inability to perform unpaid work.

Table 13. Cost-effectiveness analysis with a time horizon of 6 months from the societal perspective for each pilot site and the weighted average of the total sample (n=1189)

	n	n weight	Δ Societal costs (= Δ Healthcare costs + Δ Productivity costs) per participant (euro)	Δ Utility score	'ICER' (Δ Societal costs / Δ Utility score)
the Netherlands	247	0.21	-698	-0.004	172,880

France	124	0.10	110	0.072	1,525
Italy	200	0.17	-570	0.029	-19,372
Spain	343	0.29	-336	-0.011	30,612
United Kingdom	275	0.23	-1960	0.030	-64,677
Total*	1189	1	-780	0.015	-50,397

Abbreviations: ICER=incremental cost-effectiveness ratio

*Weighted n-average of the five countries

Costs of implementation

In the calculations above, only changes in healthcare utilization and changes in productivity losses over the 6 months are taken into account. However, implementation of the CDSMP intervention obviously also involves costs. We have made an estimation of the costs for participant recruitment, organizing the workshop sessions and giving these sessions (salary of trainers, student's dossier book, kits, SRMC license). These costs are estimated to be on average 60 euro per participant.

So, with costs of 60 euro and a societal saving of 780 euro, the net costs would be a saving of 720 euro per participant.

Budget impact analysis

A budget impact analysis (BIA) is helpful to estimate the financial consequences of implementing an intervention in a whole region or country. By extrapolating the mean societal costs per participant to the prevalence of the target population in a specific country, a BIA estimates the societal cost savings (or economic burden) of the intervention.

The BIA for the CDSMP intervention is presented in Table 14a for each of the five countries. The target population for the intervention was persons ≥ 18 years of age with a chronic condition and a low SEP, and their caregivers. Prevalence rates of this target population are calculated using the prevalence of persons having a chronic condition or being a caregiver as well as the prevalence of inhabitants with a low income level. **The prevalence of the target population was calculated** by multiplying the total population with the prevalence of inhabitants having a chronic condition or caregiver and the prevalence of persons with a low income, **resulting in more than 1.0 million targeted persons in the Netherlands to 6.8 million in the UK**. When multiplying these prevalences with the mean societal costs per person (Table 13), the total societal costs for implementing the CDSMP intervention are retrieved.

As first sensitivity analysis, we used not country-specific prevalence rates of inhabitants having a chronic condition and inhabitants being an caregiver (two columns in blue in Table 14a) but the mean rates of 28 EU countries (Table 14b). The retrieved estimations differ a bit: the prevalence of the target population was more than 1.1 million targeted persons in the Netherlands to 6.0 million in the UK; the estimated savings range from 11.8 billion euro for the UK to 0.78 billion in the Netherlands.

As second sensitivity analysis, we not only used the mean EU prevalence rates of inhabitants having a chronic condition and inhabitants being an caregiver, but also the n-weighted societal costs of the 5 pilot sites, i.e. 780 euro (column in orange, Table 14c). The retrieved estimations now differ largely: the estimated savings for the UK and the Netherlands are comparable to those in Table 14a and 14b, but the savings are larger for the other three countries, whose country-specific societal costs were smaller (Italy and Spain) or even positive (i.e.e. costs) (France). This second analysis uses the n-weighted societal costs taken from the whole sample size of the 5 pilot sites, which is the one that reaches statistical power and offer results more significant.

These sensitivity analyses show that it is difficult to obtain an accurate estimation of the societal costs (or savings) of implementing the CDSMP intervention in a whole country. No doubt that it is relevant to consider a sample size high enough (Table 14c) to reduce disturbances that can give not significant results.

An important note regarding this BIA is that several assumptions underlie these estimations; so these values are tentative and need to be interpreted with caution.

In addition to that and as mentioned before, only changes in healthcare utilization and changes in productivity losses over the 6 months are taken into account in this BIA. Costs of the implementation was estimated to be on average 60 euro per participant.

Table 14a. Budget impact analysis of the CDSMP intervention for each country

	<i>Inhabitants having a chronic condition (%)[†]</i>	<i>Inhabitants caregiver (%)[‡]</i>	Inhabitants having a chronic condition or caregiver (%) [§]	Inhabitants with low income level (%) [*]	Population [~]	Calculated prevalence of target population	Mean societal costs per participant (euro)	Total societal costs for implementation in country (euro)
the Netherlands	32.4	18	45.0	13.3	17,232,000	1,031,335	-698	-719,812,346
France	38.4	16	49.6	13.4	66,966,000	4,450,828	110	489,792,487
Italy	15.4	17	27.3	20.3	60,422,000	3,348,527	-570	-1,907,482,843
Spain	33.0	16	44.2	21.5	46,798,000	4,447,214	-336	-1,495,837,194
United Kingdom	41.7	19	55.0	18.6	66,460,000	6,798,858	-1960	-13,322,371,688

[†] Prevalence rates of 'People having a long-standing illness or health problem' of 2018, retrieved from the European Commission:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/health/data/database>

[‡] Prevalence rates of informal carers of 2016, retrieved from the European Quality of Life Survey (EQLS) 2016:

<https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=738&langId=en&pubId=8106&furtherPubs=yes>

[§] This is calculated from the prevalence of persons having a chronic condition and the prevalence (two columns left), assuming that 30% of the caregivers have a chronic condition themselves; i.e. % chronic condition + (0.7 * % caregiver)

^{*} At-risk-of-poverty rate: 'the share of people with an equivalised disposable income (after social transfer) below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold, which is set at 60% of the national median equivalised disposable income after social transfers'; of 2018 retrieved from Eurostat:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tespm010/default/table?lang=en>

[~] Population numbers of 2018 retrieved from the Worldbank: www.worldbank.org

Table 14b. Budget impact analysis of the CDSMP intervention for each country, using mean rates of EU countries of inhabitants having a chronic condition and being a caregiver

	<i>Inhabitants having a chronic condition (%)[†]</i>	<i>Inhabitants caregiver (%)[‡]</i>	Inhabitants having a chronic condition or caregiver (%) [§]	Inhabitants with low income level (%) [*]	Population [~]	Calculated prevalence of target population	Mean societal costs per participant (euro)	Total societal costs for implementation in country (euro)
the Netherlands	37.0	17	48.9	13.3	17,232,000	1,120,718	-698	-782,196,083
France	37.0	17	48.9	13.4	66,966,000	4,388,014	110	482,880,093
Italy	37.0	17	48.9	20.3	60,422,000	5,997,911	-570	-3,416,700,037
Spain	37.0	17	48.9	21.5	46,798,000	4,920,108	-336	-1,654,896,805
United Kingdom	37.0	17	48.9	18.6	66,460,000	6,044,803	-1960	-11,844,799,556

[†] Mean prevalence rate of 28 EU countries (37.0%) of 'People having a long-standing illness or health problem' of 2018, retrieved from the European Commission: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/health/data/database>

[‡] Mean prevalence rate of 28 EU countries (17%) of informal carers of 2016, retrieved from the European Quality of Life Survey (EQLS) 2016:

<https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=738&langId=en&pubId=8106&furtherPubs=yes>

\$ This is calculated from the prevalence of persons having a chronic condition and the prevalence (two columns left), assuming that 30% of the caregivers have a chronic condition themselves; i.e. % chronic condition + (0.7 * % caregiver)

* At-risk-of-poverty rate: 'the share of people with an equivalised disposable income (after social transfer) below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold, which is set at 60% of the national median equivalised disposable income after social transfers'; of 2018 retrieved from Eurostat:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tespm010/default/table?lang=en>

~ Population numbers of 2018 retrieved from the Worldbank: www.worldbank.org

Table 14c. Budget impact analysis of the CDSMP intervention for each country, using mean rates of EU countries of inhabitants having a chronic condition or being an caregiver and using the weighted average of societal costs of the 5 pilot sites

	<i>Inhabitants having a chronic condition (%)</i> †	<i>Inhabitants caregiver (%)</i> ‡	Inhabitants having a chronic condition or caregiver (%)\$	Inhabitants with low income level (%)*	Population~	Calculated prevalence of target population	Mean societal costs per participant (euro) [^]	Total societal costs for implementation in country (euro)
the Netherlands	37.0	17	48.9	13.3	17232000	1120718	780	-874,159,716
France	37.0	17	48.9	13.4	66966000	4388014	780	-3,422,651,010
Italy	37.0	17	48.9	20.3	60422000	5997911	780	-4,678,370,326
Spain	37.0	17	48.9	21.5	46798000	4920108	780	-3,837,684,029
United Kingdom	37.0	17	48.9	18.6	66460000	6044803	780	-4,714,946,215

† Mean prevalence rate of 28 EU countries (37.0%) of 'People having a long-standing illness or health problem' of 2018, retrieved from the European Commission: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/health/data/database>

‡ Mean prevalence rate of 28 EU countries (17%) of informal carers of 2016, retrieved from the European Quality of Life Survey (EQLS) 2016:

<https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=738&langId=en&pubId=8106&furtherPubs=yes>

\$ This is calculated from the prevalence of persons having a chronic condition and the prevalence (two columns left), assuming that 30% of the caregivers have a chronic condition themselves; i.e. % chronic condition + (0.7 * % caregiver)

* At-risk-of-poverty rate: 'the share of people with an equivalised disposable income (after social transfer) below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold, which is set at 60% of the national median equivalised disposable income after social transfers'; of 2018 retrieved from Eurostat:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tespm010/default/table?lang=en>

~ Population numbers of 2018 retrieved from the Worldbank: www.worldbank.org

[^] The n-weighted average of the societal costs of the 5 pilot sites (780 euro) is used.

Objective 4 Participant satisfaction

To what extent is the target population satisfied with the CDSMP intervention as a whole as well as with specific elements (problem solving, decision making, and confidence building)?

Results regarding satisfaction assessment are presented in Table 15. In general, the majority of participants did at least one activity to improve their health (>77.9%) and did not let the health problems control their life (>78.4%). Around half of the participants reported that the CDSMP intervention helped them to improve their ability to make decisions and express themselves as well as to improve communication with their family, friends and others. However, the percentage of Dutch participants who reported improvement in decision making, expression of themselves and communication with family, friends and others was lower than those of the other countries. Improvement in confidence in understanding their needs by the health system was reported by 45.7% in the total sample. The average satisfaction score was 8.30 ± 1.71 on a scale from 0 to 10; all countries rated the CDSMP intervention above 7.0.

Table 15. Satisfaction assessment of the CDSMP intervention in EFFICHRONIC programme (n=1189)

	Total	NL	Fr	It	Sp	UK
On most days I do at least one activity to improve my health (% agree/strongly agree)	999(85.5)	199(80.9)	109(88.6)	152(77.9)	293(88.8)	246(89.8)
I do not let my health problems control my life (% agree/strongly agree)	921(80.8)	194(80.5)	94(81.0)	145(78.4)	266(82.1)	222(81.0)
Did the programme improve your ability to make decisions (% quite a bit/extremely)	657(56.7)	94(38.2)	74(61.2)	103(55.7)	187(56.3)	199(72.4)
Did the programme improve your ability to express yourself (% quite a bit/extremely)	566(49.6)	70(28.6)	70(58.8)	70(40.7)	165(49.8)	191(69.5)
Did the programme improve communication with your family, friends and others (% quite a bit/extremely)	583(51.3)	66(27.0)	68(56.7)	83(48.0)	184(56.4)	182(66.4)
Did the programme improve your confidence in the health system understanding your needs (% quite a bit/extremely)	521(45.7)	59(24.2)	55(46.2)	58(33.3)	162(49.2)	187(68.5)
How satisfied were you with the programme (scale 0-10)	8.30 ± 1.71	7.42 ± 1.33	8.09 ± 2.12	8.00 ± 2.00	8.78 ± 1.48	8.81 ± 1.47

Note: Presented as mean \pm SD or N(%)

Abbreviations: Fr, France; It, Italy; NL, the Netherlands; Sp, Spain; SD, standard deviation; UK, the United Kingdom

Missing items: On most days I do at least one activity to improve my health=21; I do not let my health problems control my life=49; Did the programme improve your ability to make decisions=30; Did the programme improve your ability to express yourself=47; Did the programme improve communication with your family, friends and others=52; Did the programme improve your confidence in the health system understanding your needs=50; On a scale from 0-10 how satisfied were you with the programme that you attended=31

Overview of expected and achieved outcomes

The schedule below shows the original targets for several indicators and its achievement.

Indicators	Target	Achieved
EO1.1 Reduction of health costs of each patient	-15 to -21%	healthcare costs: -36% productivity costs: -32% societal costs: 33%
EO1.2 Reduction of health costs of each patient (savings)	€ -50 to -90 per patient	mean healthcare costs: € -307 per participant (=saving) mean productivity costs: € -473 per participant (=saving) + mean societal costs: € -780 per participant (=saving)
EO1.3 Potential Health costs saved per country	€ -50.000 to -80.000 per year	Societal costs (€): -4,7 billion (UK), -4,6 billion (IT) -3,8 billion (SP), -3,4 billion (FR) -0,8 billion (NL)
EO1.4 Health professionals: improved communication skills and informal teaching competencies (self-reported efficacy over baseline)	+25% improved	N/A (*)
EO3.1 Patients: reduced hospitalization	-10%	-0.35 nights (-42%)
EO3.2 Patients: reduced experience of medical error	-17%	-8.3%
EO3.3 Patients: Improved communication between patient and practitioner	+15%	+0.17 point (+8.3%)
EO3.4 Patients: enhanced confidence in the NHS	+10%	+45.7%
EO3.5 Patients: enhanced medication adherence	+20%	+2.5%
EO3.6 Patients: enhanced intrapersonal communication skills	+10 to +30%	Ability to express yourself: +49.6% Communication with others: +51.3%
EO3.7 Patients: physical activity and/or exercise (over baseline of the participants as a group)	+15%	Stretching/strengthening: +1.0 min/wk (+2.8%) Aerobic exercise: +2.8 min/wk (+1.8%)
EO3.8 Patients: enhanced stress management (over baseline of the participants as a group)	+40%	Anxiety / depressive feelings (item B7 of baseline questionnaire / item 5 of EQ-5D-5L): -4.2% Confidence in controlling emotional distress (item G3 of baseline questionnaire / item 3 of CDSE-6): +3.9% Depressive symptoms (items G7 of baseline questionnaire / PHQ-8 ≥10): -15.3% Trouble falling/staying asleep or sleeping too much (item 3 of PHQ-8): -8.6% Trouble concentrating (item 7 of PHQ-8): -11.3%
EO3.9 Patients: critical thinking and improved selection of information (over baseline of the participants as a group)	+10%	Ability to find good health information: +2.2% Understanding information to know what to do: +4.8%

(*) This data has been analyzed following a qualitative perspective and its analysis will be included in the Final Report.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

This evaluation study of the EFFICHRONIC project aimed to appraise the potential benefits of the CDSMP intervention for vulnerable citizens with a chronic condition with a low SEP and their caregivers over a 6-month period. Of the 2759 recruited persons, 1825 participated in at least four of six sessions of the CDSMP programme and filled out the baseline questionnaire. Of them, 1189 participants also filled out the follow-up questionnaire after six months.

It was shown that in the total sample, the intervention resulted in statistically significant improvements in several outcome measures, including self-management, swimming, sedentary behaviour, alcohol use, depressive symptoms and HR-QoL. In addition, significant improvements were found for health literacy (understanding information), communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors. In stratified analyses, it was shown that most improvements were more pronounced in women and in younger participants (<65 y). The effects in the total sample were not always found in each pilot site separately; however, it should be noted that the numbers for analyses in each pilot site separately are relatively low so should be interpreted with caution. Also, the effects on some outcome measures were inconsistently different according to whether the follow-up questionnaire was filled in before or after the COVID-19 outbreak.

The cost-effectiveness of the CDSMP intervention was studied from both a healthcare perspective and a societal perspective. After 6 months, the intervention resulted in a mean saving of 307 euro per participant in healthcare costs. For productivity costs, this was 473 euro per participant (260 euro from lost productivity at paid work; 267 euro from lost productivity at unpaid work). When combining these costs (societal perspective), the total saving is on average 780 euro per participant. The costs of the CDSMP intervention were estimated to be on average 60 euro per participant, resulting in a net saving of 720 euro per participant. The improvement in HR-QoL (health utility) was statistically significant (+0.015 points).

After the intervention period of 6 months, satisfaction of the participants was assessed. The persons with a chronic condition and caregivers were positive over the CDSMP intervention as a whole. There was variation in the evaluation on specific elements between the pilot sites but overall, the satisfaction with the programme was high.

The number of recruited persons having a chronic condition or being a caregiver (n=2759) was large. The majority of the recruited persons attended four or more sessions of the CDSMP intervention. Some participants did not fill in the baseline or follow-up questionnaire. This might be due to the fact that low SEP citizens are relatively less interested in participating in community-based interventions, training programmes and research actions [17, 18], and some of them are illiterate, making it more difficult to complete the self-administered questionnaires. In total, 1189 (65.2%) participants filled in both the baseline and the follow-up questionnaire, resulting in a number sufficient for the analyses.

The sample for analysis of 1189 participants had a mean age of 61y and consisted of two-thirds females. The socio-demographic characteristics showed that the sample differed in all characteristics by pilot site, indicating that a diverse group of chronic patients and caregivers was included. This may have contributed to differences in the site-specific findings.

The findings regarding objective 1 are in line with our hypotheses. The CDSMP intervention provided participants with a greater ability to self-manage the chronic condition, less sedentary behaviour, less depressive symptoms and a more favourable HR-QoL. A significant effect was only shown for swimming, but not for the other physical activities. In some stratified analyses, we did observe an improvement in aerobic exercise (in women, in France participants, and in participants filling in the follow-up questionnaire after the COVID-19 outbreak). Also, in the total sample and in some subgroups, time spend sedentary (during the whole week) was improved. This illustrates that physical activity and sedentary behaviour are distinct concepts that need to be targeted. Furthermore, with regard to the total sample, no effects on the intake of fruit and vegetables were found; only participants of after the COVID-19 outbreak had an increased vegetables intake, and only Dutch and British participants showed an increase in having breakfast. We found, overall, no reductions in sleep problems and fatigue or greater adherence to medication.

Regarding objective 2, our hypotheses were confirmed by the results. The intervention improved health literacy (in terms of understanding information) and communication with healthcare providers, and it reduced the number of experienced medical errors. The stratified results showed more effects in women and younger participants. When the analyses were performed per pilot

site, most effects were attenuated to non-significant, most likely due to the relatively low statistical power in the subgroups. The COVID-19 outbreak affected the effects on health literacy and experience of medical errors inconsistently.

Our hypothesis on the cost-effectiveness of the intervention was confirmed. Benefits for the society by the intervention include a reduced use of healthcare resources and greater productivity. Though, the estimations of the savings in societal costs showed a large variation between the pilot sites; the UK showed the largest saving (4.7 billion euro) and The Netherlands the smallest one (0.8 billion euro). Last, our hypothesized satisfaction score for the intervention (≥ 7 out of 10) was confirmed: participants were positive about the programme with a mean score of 8.3.

Many previous studies have examined the effect of the CDSMP programme in other populations or specific patient groups. A review of trials in young older adults (75% were aged between 49 and 65 years) with heterogeneous chronic diseases found positive effects of the CDSMP programme on physical exercise, self-efficacy, fatigue, but not on healthy diet, smoking, discomfort and anxiety. No changes were observed for healthcare utilization [9]. A more recent meta-analysis of CDSMP studies, conducted in English-speaking countries, found small to moderate improvements in communication with physician and moderate effects for psychological outcomes, such as depression and self-efficacy. Changes in physical health status, including fatigue and self-rated health, were inconsistent, and few significant changes in healthcare utilization were found. The included studies had a mean number of years of education of 12.7 [32]. A meta-analysis on physical activity in various populations showed that peer-led self-management programs increased physical activity but the effect size was small [33]. A recent meta-analysis on lay-led self-management programs and healthcare utilisation showed mixed results: a significant reduction in emergency department visits but non-significant changes in doctor visits and hospital admission [34].

Overall, our findings in a study population of persons with a low SEP are quite similar to the findings of previous literature in general populations. Contrasts lie in that we did not find a significant improvement in most physical activities in the total sample, The COVID-19 outbreak seems to influence the change in physical activity as well, although not consistently. Another contrast with previous studies is that we did observe improvements in communication with healthcare providers and substantial reductions in healthcare utilization. This latter shows that our expectation – the intervention achieves greater health gains in a vulnerable population with a low SEP compared to non vulnerable citizens – is partly confirmed.

This study has several strengths. First, the CDSMP intervention was implemented in five distinct regions of European countries, spread over Europe, with each having its own health system and culture. The country-specific findings should be interpreted with caution, however, given the relatively low numbers for analysis. Second, to our knowledge this is one of the first European studies aimed at implementing an evidence-based intervention specifically in vulnerable citizens with a low SEP. It showed that recruitment of this target population is challenging but that the intervention has significant effects on several health factors, communication with health professionals and healthcare utilization, of which some larger than in the general population. Third, the study provides insight into the societal cost savings resulting from a reduction in healthcare utilization and productivity losses.

Finally, we also mention some limitations and methodological considerations of the study. First, recruitment of citizens with a low SEP was challenging, particularly in the countries which were unfamiliar with the CDSMP programme. Second, although we included many outcome measures, the number of topics included in the questionnaire was limited. So, we might have missed relevant variables. Other variables could be considered for future studies. Third, the cost-effectiveness analyses need to be interpreted with caution, because adequate estimations of the costs (e.g. unit prices) were challenging and because of some low numbers of cases. Last, the outbreak of the COVID-19 virus worldwide may have influenced the results in persons who filled in the follow-up questionnaire after the outbreak. We tried to examine this influence of the pandemic by performing stratified analyses and saw differences in the effects on some outcome measures; though, these results were not consistent.

To conclude, as part of the EFFICHRONIC project, the 6-month CDSMP intervention in persons with a chronic condition with a low SEP or their caregivers showed benefits on several relevant outcome measures, including self-management, swimming, sedentary behaviour, alcohol use, depressive symptoms and HR-QoL. Health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors were also improved. The intervention resulted in a mean saving of 780 euro in societal costs per

participant (307 euro healthcare costs and 473 euro productivity costs). Participants' satisfaction with the CDSMP intervention was high.

Future studies on the CDSMP programme in populations with a low SEP are warranted. These studies preferably include a control group. Also, a longer follow-up period is recommended to see how long the effects will last. It is also recommended to include objective measures of physical and mental health.

As the high prevalence of chronic conditions will pose a challenge for European health systems, new ways of achieving sustainable health systems are necessary. Our study supports the hypothesis that the CDSMP intervention can contribute to the ability of citizens with a chronic condition and a low SEP to take care of themselves with better outcomes.

REFERENCES

1. WHO, *Global status report on noncommunicable diseases 2014*. 2014: Switzerland.
2. WHO, *Global action plan for the prevention and control of NCDs 2013-2020*. 2013: Switzerland.
3. Dahlgreen, G. and M. Whitehead, *Policies and strategies to promote social equity in health*. 1991, Stockholm: Institute of Future Studies.
4. Sambamoorthi, U., X. Tan, and A. Deb, *Multiple chronic conditions and healthcare costs among adults*. *Expert Rev Pharmacoecon Outcomes Res*, 2015. **15**(5): p. 823-32.
5. Collaborators, G.B.D.R.F., *Global, regional, and national comparative risk assessment of 79 behavioural, environmental and occupational, and metabolic risks or clusters of risks, 1990-2015: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2015*. *Lancet*, 2016. **388**(10053): p. 1659-1724.
6. Lin, C.C., et al., *Effects of a self-management program on patients with early-stage chronic kidney disease: a pilot study*. *Appl Nurs Res*, 2013. **26**(3): p. 151-6.
7. *Articles about the Chronic Disease Self-Management Program* [cited 2018; Available from: <https://www.selfmanagementresource.com/resources/bibliography/cdsmp>].
8. Lorig, K.R., et al., *Effect of a self-management program on patients with chronic disease*. *Eff Clin Pract*, 2001. **4**(6): p. 256-62.
9. Jonker, A.A., et al., *Promotion of self-management in vulnerable older people: a narrative literature review of outcomes of the Chronic Disease Self-Management Program (CDSMP)*. *Eur J Ageing*, 2009. **6**(4): p. 303-314.
10. Paone, D., *Factors Supporting Implementation among CDSMP Organizations*. *Front Public Health*, 2014. **2**: p. 237.
11. Liddy, C., et al., *Impact of a chronic disease self-management program on healthcare utilization in eastern Ontario, Canada*. *Prev Med Rep*, 2015. **2**: p. 586-90.
12. Ahn, S., et al., *The impact of chronic disease self-management programs: healthcare savings through a community-based intervention*. *BMC Public Health*, 2013. **13**: p. 1141.
13. Teuscher, D., et al., *A lifestyle intervention study targeting individuals with low socioeconomic status of different ethnic origins: important aspects for successful implementation*. *BMC Public Health*, 2017. **18**(1): p. 54.
14. Thompson, F.E., et al., *Interrelationships of added sugars intake, socioeconomic status, and race/ethnicity in adults in the United States: National Health Interview Survey, 2005*. *J Am Diet Assoc*, 2009. **109**(8): p. 1376-83.
15. de Munter, J.S., et al., *Cross national study of leisure-time physical activity in Dutch and English populations with ethnic group comparisons*. *Eur J Public Health*, 2013. **23**(3): p. 440-6.
16. Marshall, S.J., et al., *Race/ethnicity, social class, and leisure-time physical inactivity*. *Med Sci Sports Exerc*, 2007. **39**(1): p. 44-51.
17. Horrell, L.N. and S.M. Kneipp, *Strategies for recruiting populations to participate in the chronic disease self-management program (CDSMP): A systematic review*. *Health Mark Q*, 2017. **34**(4): p. 268-283.
18. Ejiogu, N., et al., *Recruitment and retention strategies for minority or poor clinical research participants: lessons from the Healthy Aging in Neighborhoods of Diversity across the Life Span study*. *Gerontologist*, 2011. **51 Suppl 1**: p. S33-45.
19. Ory, M.G., et al., *National study of chronic disease self-management: six-month outcome findings*. *J Aging Health*, 2013. **25**(7): p. 1258-74.
20. Booth, M., *Assessment of physical activity: an international perspective*. *Res Q Exerc Sport*, 2000. **71 Suppl 2**: p. 114-20.
21. Bush, K., et al., *The AUDIT alcohol consumption questions (AUDIT-C): an effective brief screening test for problem drinking. Ambulatory Care Quality Improvement Project (ACQUIP). Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test*. *Arch Intern Med*, 1998. **158**(16): p. 1789-95.

22. Kroenke, K., et al., *The PHQ-8 as a measure of current depression in the general population*. J Affect Disord, 2009. **114**(1-3): p. 163-73.
23. Ortega Suarez, F.J., et al., *Validation on the simplified medication adherence questionnaire (SMAQ) in renal transplant patients on tacrolimus*. Nefrologia, 2011. **31**(6): p. 690-6.
24. Ware, J., Jr., M. Kosinski, and S.D. Keller, *A 12-Item Short-Form Health Survey: construction of scales and preliminary tests of reliability and validity*. Med Care, 1996. **34**(3): p. 220-33.
25. Brooks, R., *EuroQol: the current state of play*. Health Policy, 1996. **37**(1): p. 53-72.
26. Hawkins, M., et al., *The Health Literacy Questionnaire (HLQ) at the patient-clinician interface: a qualitative study of what patients and clinicians mean by their HLQ scores*. BMC Health Services Research, 2017. **17**: p. 309.
27. Lorig, K., et al., *Outcome measures for health education and other health care interventions*. 1996, Thousand Oaks CA, US: Sage Publications, Inc.
28. Lorig, K., et al., *Can a Box of Mailed Materials Achieve the Triple Aims of Health Care? The Mailed Chronic Disease Self-Management Tool Kit Study*. Health Promot Pract, 2015. **16**(5): p. 765-74.
29. Bouwmans, C., et al., *The iMTA Productivity Cost Questionnaire: A Standardized Instrument for Measuring and Valuing Health-Related Productivity Losses*. Value Health, 2015. **18**(6): p. 753-8.
30. Tan, S.S., et al., *Evaluation Design of EFFICHRONIC: The Chronic Disease Self-Management Programme (CDSMP) Intervention for Citizens with a Low Socioeconomic Position*. Int J Environ Res Public Health, 2019. **16**(11).
31. Tan, S.S., et al., *Update of the Dutch Manual for Costing in Economic Evaluations*. Int J Technol Assess Health Care, 2012. **28**(2): p. 152-8.
32. Brady, T.J., et al., *A meta-analysis of health status, health behaviors, and health care utilization outcomes of the Chronic Disease Self-Management Program*. Preventing chronic disease, 2013. **10**: p. 120112-120112.
33. Best, K.L., et al., *Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Peer-Led Self-Management Programs for Increasing Physical Activity*. International Journal of Behavioral Medicine, 2016. **23**(5): p. 527-538.
34. Lederle, M. and E.-M. Bitzer, *A close look at lay-led self-management programs for chronic diseases and health care utilisation: A systematic review and meta-analysis*. German medical science : GMS e-journal, 2019. **17**: p. Doc03-Doc03.

ANNEX 1 BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRE

English version used in the United Kingdom:

BASELINE MEASUREMENT

First name and surname:

Address:

Postcode:

E-mail address:

Telephone number:

Date:

Signature

Please leave blank

Country code

Participant number

INSTRUCTIONS FOR COMPLETING THE QUESTIONNAIRE

- Please answer all the questions, even if they seem to be the same: these questions help us to view the situation again from a different angle.
- Please select only one answer per question. If it is possible to select more than one answer, this will be mentioned for this specific question.
- Please answer the questionnaire with a blue or black pen.
- When you are done, please check that you have not forgotten any questions.

MAKING A MISTAKE.

If you select a wrong box and want to correct it, colour the wrong box black.

Example:

- You select a wrong box and want to correct it

For example:

You are a woman

What is your Gender?

- Male
 Female

- Corrected: you have now answered that you are female

What is your Gender?

- Male
 Female

Text or numbers should be filled in within the box:

How many cups of coffee did you drink yesterday?

Correct

Wrong

Please leave blank

Country code

Participant number

A. YOUR HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

This section asks for your views about your state of health. This information will demonstrate how you feel and how well you are able to do your usual activities. Answer each question by choosing just one answer. If you are unsure how to answer a question, please give the best answer you can.

A1 In general, would you say your health is

- Excellent
- Very good
- Good
- Fair
- Poor

The following questions are about activities you might do during a typical day.

Does your state of health now limit you in the following activities? If so, how much?

	Yes, limited a lot	Yes, limited a little	No, not limited at all
A2 Moderate activities, such as housework, swimming or cycling	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A3 Climbing several flights of stairs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

During the past 4 weeks, have you had any of the following problems with your work or other regular daily activities as a result of your physical health?

How much of the time during the past 4 weeks:

	All of the time	Most of the time	Some of the time	A little of the time	None of the time
A4 Have you accomplished less than you would like	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A5 Were you limited in the kind of work or other activities that you could do	<input type="checkbox"/>				

During the past 4 weeks, have you had any of the following problems with your work or other regular daily activities as a result of any emotional issues (such as feeling unhappy or anxious)?

	All of the time	Most of the time	Some of the time	A little of the time	None of the time
A6 Accomplished less than you would like	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A7 Were limited in the kind of work or other activities that you could do	<input type="checkbox"/>				

A8 During the past 4 weeks, how much did pain interfere with your normal work or other regular daily activities?

- Not at all
- A little bit
- Moderately
- Quite a bit
- Extremely

How much of the time during the past 4 weeks:

	All of the time	Most of the time	Some of the time	A little of the time	None of the time
A9 Have you felt calm & peaceful	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A10 Did you have a lot of energy	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A11 Have you felt anxious	<input type="checkbox"/>				

A12 During the past 4 weeks, how much have your physical health or emotional wellbeing interfered with your normal social activities with family, friends, neighbours, or social groups?

- All of the time
- Most of the time
- Some of the time
- A little of the time
- None of the time

B. YOUR QUALITY OF LIFE

B1 We are interested in learning whether or not you are affected by sleep problems. Please circle the number below that describes your sleep in the past week:

B2 We are interested in learning whether or not you are affected by fatigue. Please circle the number below that describes your fatigue in the past week

B3 Please tick the one box that best describes your health today:

- I have no problems in walking
- I have slight problems in walking
- I have moderate problems in walking
- I have severe problems in walking
- I am unable to walk

B4 Please tick the one box that best describes your health today:

- I have no problems washing or dressing myself
- I have slight problems washing or dressing myself
- I have moderate problems washing or dressing myself
- I have severe problems washing or dressing myself
- I am unable to wash or dress myself

B5 Please tick the one box that best describes your health today:

- I have no problems doing my usual activities
- I have slight problems doing my usual activities
- I have moderate problems doing my usual activities
- I have severe problems doing my usual activities
- I am unable to do my usual activities

B6 Please tick the one box that best describes your health today:

- I have no pain or discomfort
- I have slight pain or discomfort
- I have moderate pain or discomfort
- I have severe pain or discomfort
- I have extreme pain or discomfort

B7 Please tick the one box that best describes your health today:

- I am not anxious or depressed
- I am slightly anxious or depressed
- I am moderately anxious or depressed
- I am severely anxious or depressed
- I am extremely anxious or depressed

- We would like to know how good or bad your health is TODAY.
- This scale is numbered from 0 to 100.
- 100 means the best health you can imagine.
0 means the worst health you can imagine.
- Mark an X on the scale to indicate how your health is TODAY.
- Now, please write the number you marked on the scale in the box below.

YOUR HEALTH TODAY =

The best health
you can imagine

The worst health
you can imagine

C. YOUR LIFESTYLE

C1 How many days do you eat breakfast per week?

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
<input type="checkbox"/>							

C2 How many servings of fresh vegetables do you usually eat?

One serving corresponds to one serving spoon

* Examples of vegetables are: green beans, carrots, broccoli, sprouts, tomatoes, lettuce, spinach, leek, or cucumber.

- Less than 1 per week
- 1-2 per week
- 3-4 per week
- 5-6 per week
- 1-2 per day
- 3 or more per day

C3 How many servings of fresh fruit do you usually eat?

One serving corresponds to one handful.

* Examples of servings of fruit are: an apple, a pear, a kiwi, a banana, an orange, a handful of strawberries, a handful of berries, or a handful of grapes.

- Less than 1 per week
- 1-2 per week
- 3-4 per week
- 5-6 per week
- 1-2 per day
- 3 or more per day

C4 How often do you have a drink containing alcohol?

- Never
- 1-2 per month
- 3-4 per month
- 5-6 per month
- 1-2 per week
- 3 or more per week

C5 Do you smoke at the present time?

- Yes
- No

C6 During the past week, even if it was not a typical week for you, how much total time (for the entire week) did you spend on each of the following? (Please provide *one* number for each question.)

Per week	None	Less than 30 minutes/ week	30-60 minutes/ week	1-3 hours/week	More than 3 hours/week
1. Stretching or strengthening exercises (such as using weights, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Walking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Swimming or aquatic exercise	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Bicycling (including stationary exercise bikes)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Other exercise equipment (rowing machine, treadmill etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. On other exercise (specify) :	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

C7 The next question is about the time you spent sitting during the past week. Include time spent at work, at home, while doing course work and during leisure time. This may include time spent sitting at a desk, visiting friends, reading, or sitting or lying down to watch television.

a. During the past week, how much time did you spend sitting on a weekday?

Number of hours per day:

b. During the past week, how much time did you spend sitting on a weekend day?

Number of hours per day:

C8 You are participating in the workshop sessions as:

- a person with a long-term condition (please carry on to Section D)
- a caregiver (Please go to Question E5 half way through Section E. Please note that these questions in Section E refer to the person that you care for)

D. YOUR MEDICATION USE

Please go to section E if you don't take any medicines

The following questions refer to any medication you regularly take for your long-term condition

D1 Do you always take your medication at the specified time?

- Yes
 No

D2 When you feel ill, have you ever discontinued taking your medication?

- Yes
 No

D3 Have you ever forgotten to take your medication?

- Yes
 No

D4 Have you ever forgotten to take your medication during the weekend?

- Yes
 No

D5 In the past week, how many times did you fail to take your prescribed dose?

- Never
 1-2 times
 3-5 times
 6-10 times
 More than 10 times

D6 Since your last medical visit, how many whole days have gone by in which you did not take your medication?

Number of days:

E. THE CARE YOU RECEIVE

The following questions refer to the care you receive for any reason (not specifically your long-term condition).

E1 In the past 6 months, how many times did you visit a doctor (GP or specialist, at a doctor's practice or hospital's outpatient department)?

Do not include visits while in a hospital or to a hospital's Accident and Emergency Department

- Never
 Number of times:

E2 In the past 6 months, how many times did you go to a hospital's Accident and Emergency Department?

- Never
 Number of times:

E3 How many different times did you stay in a hospital overnight or longer in the past 6 months?

- Never
 Number of times:

E4 How many total nights did you spend in a hospital in the past 6 months?

- Never
 Number of nights in total in the past 6 months:

E5 When you visit your doctor, how often do you do the following

Please circle one number for each question

	Never	Almost never	Sometimes	Fairly often	Very often	Always
1. Prepare a list of questions for your doctor	<input type="checkbox"/>					
2. Ask questions about the things you want to know and things you don't understand about your treatment	<input type="checkbox"/>					
3. Discuss any personal problems that may be related to your condition	<input type="checkbox"/>					

E6 Please indicate if you have ever personally experienced a healthcare provider not explaining things in a way you could understand and it was a problem for you:

- Yes, it is or was a major problem
- Yes, it is or was a minor problem
- No, I have not had this problem

E7 Have you ever personally experienced a medical error in your own care?

- Yes
- No (please, go to question E9)

E8 How serious a problem was this medical error for you:

- A major problem
- A minor problem
- Not a problem

E9 On a scale from very easy to very difficult, how easy would you say it is to find information on the treatment of your condition?

Very easy	Fairly easy	Fairly difficult	Very difficult	Don't know
<input type="checkbox"/>				

E10 On a scale from very easy to very difficult, how easy would you say it is to use information the doctor gives you to make decisions about your condition?

Very easy	Fairly easy	Fairly difficult	Very difficult	Don't know
<input type="checkbox"/>				

F. THE SUPPORT YOU RECEIVE

F1 What kind of social relationships do you have?

Tick one box only, the most suitable one

- I have a wide range of social relationships in the community.
- I relate to family and neighbours/friends and leave the house.
- I relate to family and leave the house.
- I don't leave the house but do receive visits (once or more a week).
- I don't leave the house and don't receive visits (or less than once a week).

F2 What kind of social support do you have?

Tick one box only, the most suitable one

- I don't need any support.
- I receive support from family, neighbours and/or friends.
- I receive voluntary assistance or home support.
- I receive support in a residential care setting.
- I need support, but I don't receive it.

For **unpaid work**, you might be bothered by physical or psychological problems. Sometimes as a result you (might) do less. For example you could have trouble caring for your children or doing voluntary work. Or you are unable to run errands and pick up groceries, or to work in the garden. The following questions refer to this.

F3 Were there days in the last 4 weeks during which you were forced to do less unpaid work because of physical or psychological problems?

- Yes
- No (Please go to section G)

F4 How many days in the last 4 weeks did this happen?

Number of days:

F5 If somebody (for example your partner, family member or friend) helped you on these days, and he or she did all the unpaid work that you were unable to do for yourself how many hours on average did that person spend doing this on these days?

Number of hours:

G. YOUR EMOTIONAL HEALTH

Please rate each of the following statements on a scale of 0 to 10, where 0 is 'not sure at all' and 10 is 'totally sure'. Please circle the number that best describes your confidence.

G1 How sure are you that you can keep any fatigue caused by your long-term condition from interfering with the things you want to do?

G2 How sure are you that you can keep any physical discomfort or pain of your condition from interfering with the things you want to do?

G3 How sure are you that you can keep any emotional distress caused by your condition from interfering with the things you want to do?

G4 How sure are you that you can keep any other symptoms or health problems you have from interfering with the things you want to do?

G5 How sure are you that you can do the different tasks and activities needed to manage your condition so as to reduce you need to see a doctor?

G6 How sure are you that you can do things other than just taking medication to reduce how much your condition affects your everyday life?

G7 Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following problems?

	Not at all	Several days	More than half the days	Nearly every day
1. Little interest or pleasure in doing things	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Feeling tired or having little energy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Poor appetite or overeating	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Feeling bad about yourself, or that you are a failure, or have let yourself or your family down	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed. Or the opposite – being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

H. YOUR PERSONAL DETAILS

H1 Which sex are you?

- Male
 Female
 Other (please specify)

H2 Date of birth

<input type="text"/>	-	<input type="text"/>	-	<input type="text"/>
Day		Month		Year

H3 In which country were you born?

- United Kingdom
 Other (Please specify):

H4 In which country was your mother born?

- United Kingdom
 Other (Please specify):

H5 In which country was your father born?

- United Kingdom
 Other (Please specify):

H6 Housing and your needs

Tick one box only, the most suitable one

- My housing is suitable for my needs
 It has reduced accessibility or architectural restrictions inside that affect my mobility
 It has dampness (or similar problems) or is not properly equipped (for example no running water, incomplete bathroom, no heating)
 There is no lift (in the case of a multi-story building) or phone
 It is not adapted but needs to be

H7 What is your household composition?

Tick one box only, the most suitable one

- I live with family or partner and I am independent
- I live alone and I am independent
- I live with family or partner and have a certain degree of dependence*
- I live alone with family nearby and I have a certain degree of dependence*
- I live alone and isolated, and I have a certain degree of dependence*

**This means that I depend on others for activities related to daily living such as: feeding, bathing, dressing and personal hygiene.*

H8 What is the highest level of education you have completed?

Tick one box only

- No education
- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Post-secondary non-university education
- Bachelor degree or equivalent
- Masters or equivalent
- Doctoral or equivalent

H9 Which category indicates your net monthly household income?

- More than £2,000 per month
- From £1,300 to £2,000 per month
- From £700 to £1,300 per month
- Less than £700 per month

H10 Below are various possible sources of income. Which kinds of income did your household receive in the past year?

Please tick all answers that apply

- Income from work (as employee or self-employed)
- Pension
- Social security benefits
- Other sources of income not mentioned above
- No source of income

If you did not receive any income from work, please go to question I1; otherwise carry on with the following questions

H11 What is your occupation?

H12 How many hours a week do you work?

Count only the hours that you get paid.

Number of hours:

H13 How many days a week do you work?

Number of days:

H14 Have you missed work in the last 4 weeks as a result of being sick?

Only count the missed work days in the last 4 weeks

Yes, I have missed days

No (Please go to question I1)

H15 Did you miss work in the period before the last 4 weeks due to being sick?

This is referring to one whole uninterrupted period of missed work as a result of being sick.

Yes

No (Please skip to question I1)

H16 How many days did this whole uninterrupted period of missed work last?

This is referring to the last whole uninterrupted period of missed work as a result of being sick.

Number of days:

I. ADDITIONAL REMARKS

I1 Did you receive help to fill out this questionnaire?

Yes, I got help from (Please tick all the answers that apply):

My partner

(One of) my children

Another family member

The workshop leader

Someone else, please specify:

No

I2 You will receive a questionnaire again in 6 months. How would you prefer to receive it?

No preference

Via e-mail. You will receive an e-mail with a link to fill out the questionnaire online. Please make sure your e-mail address is correctly stated on the front page.

Via mail. You will receive a paper version of the questionnaire, which you will be able to return to us by mail. Please make sure your mail address is correctly stated on the front page.

By hand delivery

I3 Do you have any additional remarks that have not been addressed in this survey?

Thank you for completing this questionnaire

This questionnaire is part of the project / joint action '738127 / EFFICHRONIC' which has received funding from the European Union's Health Programme (2014-2020).

ANNEX 2 FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONNAIRE

English version used in the United Kingdom:

FOLLOW-UP MEASUREMENT

INSTRUCTIONS FOR COMPLETING THE QUESTIONNAIRE

- Thank you for completing the follow-up questionnaire, the results will help us identify how well the programme works and what could be done better
- Please answer all the questions, even if they seem to be the same: these questions help us to view the situation again from a different angle.
- Please select only one answer per question with a tick or a cross. If it is possible to select more than one answer, this will be mentioned in the question.
- Please complete the questionnaire with a blue or black pen.
- When you have finished, please check that you have not forgotten any questions.

MAKING A MISTAKE

If you select a wrong box and want to correct it, colour the wrong box black and put a tick or a cross in the right box.

For example, you are a woman and accidentally put a cross in the wrong box as below:

What is your Gender?

- Male
- Female

Correct it as follows:

What is your Gender?

- Male
- Female

Text or numbers should be filled in within the box. For example:

Question: How many cups of coffee did you drink yesterday?

- Correct
- Wrong

Country code

Provider Code

Participant number

Date completed:

A. THE CHRONIC DISEASE SELF MANAGEMENT PROGRAMME

You recently took part in a chronic disease self-management programme. The following questions are about the changes you experienced after attending the programme.

EVA-1 On most days I do at least one activity to improve my health

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

EVA-2 I do not let my health problems control my life

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Did the programme improve:

EVA-3. ... your ability to make decisions?

- Extremely
- Quite a bit
- Moderately
- A little bit
- Not at all

EVA-4. ... your ability to express yourself?

- Extremely
- Quite a bit
- Moderately
- A little bit
- Not at all

EVA-5. ... communication with your family, friends and others?

- Extremely
- Quite a bit
- Moderately
- A little bit
- Not at all

EVA-6. ... your confidence in the health system understanding your needs?

- Extremely
- Quite a bit
- Moderately
- A little bit
- Not at all

EVA-7. On a scale from 0-10 how satisfied were you with the programme that you attended?

B. YOUR HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

This section asks for your views about your state of health. This information will demonstrate how you feel and how well you are able to do your usual activities. Please answer each question by choosing just one answer. If you are unsure how to answer a question, please give the best answer you can.

B1 In general, would you say your health is:

- Excellent
- Very good
- Good
- Fair
- Poor

The following questions are about activities you might do during a typical day.

Does your state of health now limit you in the following activities? If so, how much?

	Yes, limited a lot	Yes, limited a little	No, not limited at all
B2 Moderate activities, such as housework, swimming or cycling	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B3 Climbing several flights of stairs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

During the past 4 weeks, have you had any of the following problems with your work or other regular daily activities as a result of your physical health?

How much of the time during the past 4 weeks:

	All of the time	Most of the time	Some of the time	A little of the time	None of the time
B4 Have you accomplished less than you would like	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B5 Were you limited in the kind of work or other activities that you could do	<input type="checkbox"/>				

During the past 4 weeks, have you had any of the following problems with your work or other regular daily activities as a result of any emotional issues (such as feeling unhappy or anxious)?

	All of the time	Most of the time	Some of the time	A little of the time	None of the time
B6 Accomplished less than you would like	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B7 Were limited in the kind of work or other activities that you could do	<input type="checkbox"/>				

B8 During the past 4 weeks, how much did pain interfere with your normal work or other regular daily activities?

- Not at all
- A little bit
- Moderately
- Quite a bit
- Extremely

How much of the time during the past 4 weeks:

	All of the time	Most of the time	Some of the time	A little of the time	None of the time
B9 Have you felt calm & peaceful	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B10 Did you have a lot of energy	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B11 Have you felt anxious	<input type="checkbox"/>				

B12 During the past 4 weeks, how much have your physical health or emotional wellbeing interfered with your normal social activities with family, friends, neighbours, or social groups?

- All of the time
- Most of the time
- Some of the time
- A little of the time
- None of the time

C. YOUR QUALITY OF LIFE

C1 We are interested in learning whether or not you are affected by sleep problems. Please circle the number below that describes your sleep in the past week:

C2 We are interested in learning whether or not you are affected by fatigue. Please circle the number below that describes your fatigue in the past week

C3 Please tick the one box that best describes your health today:

- I have no problems in walking
- I have slight problems in walking
- I have moderate problems in walking
- I have severe problems in walking
- I am unable to walk

C4 Please tick the one box that best describes your health today:

- I have no problems washing or dressing myself
- I have slight problems washing or dressing myself
- I have moderate problems washing or dressing myself
- I have severe problems washing or dressing myself
- I am unable to wash or dress myself

C5 Please tick the one box that best describes your health today:

- I have no problems doing my usual activities
- I have slight problems doing my usual activities
- I have moderate problems doing my usual activities
- I have severe problems doing my usual activities
- I am unable to do my usual activities

C6 Please tick the one box that best describes your health today:

- I have no pain or discomfort
- I have slight pain or discomfort
- I have moderate pain or discomfort
- I have severe pain or discomfort
- I have extreme pain or discomfort

C7 Please tick the one box that best describes your health today:

- I am not anxious or depressed
- I am slightly anxious or depressed
- I am moderately anxious or depressed
- I am severely anxious or depressed
- I am extremely anxious or depressed

We would like to know how good or bad your health is TODAY.

- This scale is numbered from 0 to 100.
- 100 means the best health you can imagine.
0 means the worst health you can imagine.
- Mark an X on the scale to indicate how your health is TODAY.
- Now, please write the number you marked on the scale in the box below.

YOUR HEALTH TODAY =

The best health
you can imagine

The worst health
you can imagine

D. YOUR LIFESTYLE

D1 How many days do you eat breakfast per week?

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
<input type="checkbox"/>							

D2 How many servings of fresh vegetables do you usually eat?

One serving corresponds to one serving spoon

* *Examples of vegetables are: green beans, carrots, broccoli, sprouts, tomatoes, lettuce, spinach, leek, or cucumber.*

- Less than 1 per week
- 1-2 per week
- 3-4 per week
- 5-6 per week
- 1-2 per day
- 3 or more per day

D3 How many servings of fresh fruit do you usually eat?

One serving corresponds to one handful.

* *Examples of servings of fruit are: an apple, a pear, a kiwi, a banana, an orange, a handful of strawberries, a handful of berries, or a handful of grapes.*

- Less than 1 per week
- 1-2 per week
- 3-4 per week
- 5-6 per week
- 1-2 per day
- 3 or more per day

D4 How often do you have a drink containing alcohol?

- Never
- 1-2 per month
- 3-4 per month
- 5-6 per month
- 1-2 per week
- 3 or more per week

D5 Do you smoke at the present time?

- Yes
- No

D6 During the past week, even if it was not a typical week for you, how much total time (for the entire week) did you spend on each of the following? (Please provide *one* number for each question.)

Per week	None	Less than 30 minutes/ week	30-60 minutes/ week	1-3 hours/week	More than 3 hours/week
1. Stretching or strengthening exercises (such as using weights, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Walking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Swimming or aquatic exercise	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Cycling (including stationary exercise bikes)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Other exercise equipment (rowing machine, treadmill etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. On other exercise (specify) :	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

D7 The next question is about the time you spent sitting during the past week. Include time spent at work, at home, while doing course work and during leisure time. This may include time spent sitting at a desk, visiting friends, reading, or sitting or lying down to watch television.

a. During the past week, how much time did you spend sitting on a weekday?

Number of hours per day:

b. During the past week, how much time did you spend sitting on a weekend day?

Number of hours per day:

D8 You are participating in the workshop sessions as:

- a person with a long-term condition
- a caregiver
- both a person with a long-term condition and a caregiver

E. YOUR MEDICATION USE

Please go to section F on the next page if you don't take any medicines

The following questions refer to any medication you regularly take for your long-term condition

E1 Do you always take your medication at the specified time?

- Yes
 No

E2 When you feel ill, have you ever discontinued taking your medication?

- Yes
 No

E3 Have you ever forgotten to take your medication?

- Yes
 No

E4 Have you ever forgotten to take your medication during the weekend?

- Yes
 No

E5 In the past week, how many times did you fail to take your prescribed dose?

- Never
 1-2 times
 3-5 times
 6-10 times
 More than 10 times

E6 Since your last medical visit, how many whole days have gone by in which you did not take your medication?

Number of days:

F. THE CARE YOU RECEIVE

The following questions refer to the care you receive for any reason (not specifically your long-term condition).

F1 In the past 6 months, how many times did you visit a doctor (GP or specialist, at a doctor's practice or hospital's outpatient department)?

Do not include visits while in a hospital or to a hospital's Accident and Emergency Department

- Never
 Number of times:

F2 In the past 6 months, how many times did you go to a hospital's Accident and Emergency Department?

- Never
 Number of times:

F3 How many different times did you stay in a hospital overnight or longer in the past 6 months?

- Never
 Number of times:

F4 How many total nights did you spend in a hospital in the past 6 months?

- Never
 Number of nights in total in the past 6 months:

F5 When you visit your doctor, how often do you do the following:

Please circle one number for each question

	Never	Almost never	Sometimes	Fairly often	Very often	Always
1. Prepare a list of questions for your doctor	<input type="checkbox"/>					
2. Ask questions about the things you want to know and things you don't understand about your treatment	<input type="checkbox"/>					
3. Discuss any personal problems that may be related to your condition	<input type="checkbox"/>					

F6 Please indicate if you have personally experienced a healthcare provider not explaining things in a way you could understand and it was a problem for you in the past 6 months:

- Yes, it is or was a major problem
- Yes, it is or was a minor problem
- No, I have not had this problem

F7 Have you personally experienced a medical error in your own care in the past 6 months?

- Yes
- No (please, go to question F9)

F8 How serious a problem was this medical error for you:

- A major problem
- A minor problem
- Not a problem

F9 On a scale from very easy to very difficult, how easy would you say it is to find information on the treatment of your condition?

Very easy	Fairly easy	Fairly difficult	Very difficult	Don't know
<input type="checkbox"/>				

F10 On a scale from very easy to very difficult, how easy would you say it is to use information the doctor gives you to make decisions about your condition?

Very easy	Fairly easy	Fairly difficult	Very difficult	Don't know
<input type="checkbox"/>				

G. THE SUPPORT YOU RECEIVE

For unpaid work, you might be bothered by physical or psychological problems. Sometimes as a result you (might) do less. For example you could have trouble caring for your children or doing voluntary work. Or you are unable to run errands and pick up groceries, or to work in the garden. The following questions refer to this.

G1 Were there days in the last 4 weeks during which you were forced to do less unpaid work because of physical or psychological problems?

- Yes
 No (Please go to section H)

G2 How many days in the last 4 weeks did this happen?

Number of days:

G3 If somebody (for example your partner, family member or friend) helped you on these days, and he or she did all the unpaid work that you were unable to do for yourself how many hours on average did that person spend doing this on these days?

Number of hours:

H. YOUR EMOTIONAL HEALTH

Please rate each of the following statements on a scale of 0 to 10, where 0 is 'not sure at all' and 10 is 'totally sure'. Please circle the number that best describes your confidence.

H1 How sure are you that you can keep any fatigue caused by your long-term condition from interfering with the things you want to do?

H2 How sure are you that you can keep any physical discomfort or pain of your condition from interfering with the things you want to do?

H3 How sure are you that you can keep any emotional distress caused by your condition from interfering with the things you want to do?

H4 How sure are you that you can keep any other symptoms or health problems you have from interfering with the things you want to do?

H5 How sure are you that you can do the different tasks and activities needed to manage your condition so as to reduce you need to see a doctor?

H6 How sure are you that you can do things other than just taking medication to reduce how much your condition affects your everyday life?

H7 Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following problems?

	Not at all	Several days	More than half the days	Nearly every day
1. Little interest or pleasure in doing things	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Feeling tired or having little energy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Poor appetite or overeating	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Feeling bad about yourself, or that you are a failure, or have let yourself or your family down	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed. Or the opposite – being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

I. YOUR PERSONAL DETAILS

11 Date of birth

<input type="text"/>	-	<input type="text"/>	-	<input type="text"/>
Day		Month		Year

12 Below are various possible sources of income. Which kinds of income did your household receive in the past year?

Please tick all answers that apply

- Income from work (as employee or self-employed)
- Pension
- Social security benefits
- Other sources of income not mentioned above
- No source of income

If you did not receive any income from work, please go to question J1; otherwise carry on with the following questions

13 What is your occupation?

14 How many hours a week do you work?

Count only the hours that you get paid.

Number of hours:

15 How many days a week do you work?

Number of days:

16 Have you missed work in the last 4 weeks as a result of being sick?

Only count the missed work days in the last 4 weeks

- Yes, I have missed days
- No (Please go to question J1 on the next page)

17 Did you miss work in the period before the last 4 weeks due to being sick?

This is referring to one whole uninterrupted period of missed work as a result of being sick.

- Yes
- No (Please go to question J1 on the next page)

18 How many days did this whole uninterrupted period of missed work last?

This is referring to the last whole uninterrupted period of missed work as a result of being sick.

Number of days:

J. ADDITIONAL REMARKS

J1 Did you receive help to fill out this questionnaire?

Yes, I got help from (Please tick all the answers that apply):

- My partner
- (One of) my children
- Another family member
- The workshop leader
- Someone else, please specify:

No

J2 Do you have any additional remarks that have not been addressed in this survey?

Thank you for completing this questionnaire

This questionnaire is part of the project / joint action '738127 / EFFICHRONIC' which has received funding from the European Union's Health Programme (2014-2020).

ANNEX 3 OBJECTIVE 1: TABLES PER PILOT SITE

In Supplemental Table 4e to 4i, the results of objective 1 are shown for each pilot site. Due to the smaller sample size for each pilot site, the significance of the findings should be interpreted with caution.

Results for the Netherlands (Supplemental Table 4e) are comparable to the total sample; however, some changes were not significant in the Dutch sample (swimming, alcohol use, depressive symptoms, physical HR-QoL, utility and overall health). Significant improvements were found for having breakfast, sleep and fatigue. For France (Supplemental Table 4f), the results are very similar to those of the total sample; total aerobic exercise significantly increased, and the effects on self-management and alcohol use attenuated but this might be due to the small France sample size (n=124). Italy's results (Supplemental Table 4g) differ from those of the total sample in self-management, sedentary behaviour, alcohol use, depressive symptoms (all non-significant decreases) as well as in medication adherence (significant improvement), and mental HR-QoL and self-rated overall health (non-significant improvement). A significant improvement was found for cycling, while more sleep problems were reported (borderline significant). Spain (Supplemental Table 4h) also showed less significant effects than the total sample (self-management, swimming, sedentary behaviour, alcohol use, depressive symptoms, physical and mental HR-QoL, utility and overall health) and found a significant increase in sleep problems. Last, the UK (Supplemental Table 4i) is most comparable to the total sample with the exception of swimming (no significant increase). Besides, negative effects are the significant decreases in having breakfast and sleep, while fatigue significantly decreases (=improvement).

Supplemental Table 4e. the Netherlands - Self-management, healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, medication adherence and HR-QoL of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up (n=247)

	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Self-management				
CDSE-6 (score range 1-10) [§]	240	6.71±1.76	6.91±1.85	0.042*
Lifestyle factors				
Physical exercise				
Stretching/strengthening (min/wk)	236	27.97±53.75	28.28±51.50	0.930*
Aerobic exercise (min/wk)	246	211.95±137.56	210.73±126.10	0.879*
Walk for exercise (min/wk)	237	106.96±64.67	101.90±65.87	0.229*
Swimming or aquatic exercise (min/wk)	231	8.70±30.55	10.00±34.82	0.546*
Bicycling (min/wk)	237	66.58±67.78	69.30±71.56	0.506*
Other aerobic exercise (min/wk)	238	36.37±61.69	34.35±60.35	0.627*
Sedentary behaviour (week day) (min/wk)	232	7.57±3.04	7.05±3.07	0.003*
Sedentary behaviour (weekend day) (min/wk)	235	6.92±3.07	6.52±3.02	0.048*
Fruit, >1 portion/d	247	125(50.61)	119(48.18)	0.461†
Vegetables, >1 portion/d	245	104(42.45)	118(48.16)	0.093†
Having breakfast, >5 d/wk	238	165(69.33)	205(86.13)	<.001†
Alcohol, 2 times/wk or more	247	84(34.01)	81(32.79)	0.648†
Smoking, yes	246	26(10.57)	24(9.76)	0.625†
Depressive symptoms (PHQ-8 ≥10)	232	43(18.53)	39(16.81)	0.626†
Sleep problems (score range 0-10) [‡]	244	4.39±2.94	3.98±2.84	0.018*
Fatigue (score range 0-10) [‡]	244	5.09±2.83	4.65±2.80	0.002*
Medication adherence (SMAQ), no adherence	143	91(63.63)	88(61.54)	0.742†
HR-QoL				

PCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) §	238	46.82±9.96	47.05±9.88	0.609*
MCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) §	238	42.22±9.59	44.45±8.97	<.001*
EQ-5D-5L utility values#	246	0.85±0.18	0.84±0.17	0.545*
EQ-5D-5L overall health (score range 0-100) §	245	72.20±17.20	73.66±17.24	0.083*

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

Range from less than 0 (where 0 is the value of a health state equivalent to dead; negative values representing values worse than dead) to 1 (the value of full health), with higher scores indicating higher health utility.

Abbreviations: CDSE-6, short 6-item Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument; HR-QoL, Health-related quality of life; PHQ-8, 8-item Patient Health Questionnaire; SMAQ, short 6-item Medication Adherence Questionnaire; MCS, Mental Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; PCS, Physical Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; SF-12, 12-item Short form

Supplemental Table 4f. France - Self-management, healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, medication adherence and HR-QoL of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up (n=124)

	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Self-management				
CDSE-6 (score range 1-10) §	115	6.04±1.98	6.34±2.13	0.085*
Lifestyle factors				
Physical exercise				
Stretching/strengthening (min/wk)	109	39.63±60.95	46.10±64.28	0.217*
Aerobic exercise (min/wk)	122	135.25±107.58	166.48±140.97	0.006*
Walk for exercise (min/wk)	118	88.09±67.92	97.25±69.88	0.117*
Swimming or aquatic exercise (min/wk)	108	5.14±16.81	17.36±38.21	0.001*
Bicycling (min/wk)	110	20.45±45.28	24.95±51.01	0.236*
Other aerobic exercise (min/wk)	110	28.77±61.47	34.77±68.87	0.429*
Sedentary behaviour (week day) (min/wk)	104	5.99±3.49	5.46±3.28	0.043*
Sedentary behaviour (weekend day) (min/wk)	101	5.96±3.26	5.04±2.54	0.005*
Fruit, >1 portion/d	123	49(39.84)	47(38.21)	0.864†
Vegetables, >1 portion/d	123	42(34.15)	48(39.02)	0.391†
Having breakfast, >5 d/wk	118	80(67.80)	82(69.49)	0.815†
Alcohol, 2 times/wk or more	123	24(19.51)	20(16.26)	0.503†
Smoking, yes	115	27(23.48)	28(24.35)	1.000†
Depressive symptoms (PHQ-8 ≥10)	96	43(44.79)	29(30.21)	0.014†
Sleep problems (score range 0-10) ‡	120	5.56±2.94	5.40±3.09	0.510*
Fatigue (score range 0-10) ‡	120	6.26±2.64	5.94±2.59	0.131*
Medication adherence (SMAQ), no adherence	95	52(54.74)	48(50.53)	0.503†
HR-QoL				
PCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) §	104	37.86±10.61	39.99±10.75	0.008*
MCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) §	104	39.32±9.75	42.67±10.11	<.001*
EQ-5D-5L utility values#	121	0.56±0.32	0.63±0.30	<.001*
EQ-5D-5L Overall health (score range 0-100) §	116	56.21±21.22	61.10±18.96	0.007*

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

Range from less than 0 (where 0 is the value of a health state equivalent to dead; negative values representing values worse than dead) to 1 (the value of full health), with higher scores indicating higher health utility.

Abbreviations: CDSE-6, short 6-item Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument; HR-QoL, Health-related quality of life; PHQ-8, 8-item Patient Health Questionnaire; SMAQ, short 6-item Medication Adherence Questionnaire; MCS, Mental Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; PCS, Physical Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; SF-12, 12-item Short form

Supplemental Table 4g. Italy - Self-management, healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, medication adherence and HR-QoL of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up (n=200)

	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Self-management				
CDSE-6 (score range 1-10)§	167	7.28±1.83	7.21±1.82	0.563*
Lifestyle factors				
Physical exercise				
Stretching/strengthening (min/wk)	164	50.94±73.55	49.76±65.91	0.814*
Aerobic exercise (min/wk)	194	147.76±107.76	156.80±115.13	0.280*
Walk for exercise (min/wk)	191	103.43±69.32	104.61±65.28	0.833*
Swimming or aquatic exercise (min/wk)	150	12.30±39.67	14.30±40.54	0.396*
Bicycling (min/wk)	151	10.53±32.53	16.49±41.23	0.047*
Other aerobic exercise (min/wk)	151	30.70±65.00	28.11±60.41	0.600*
Sedentary behaviour (week day) (min/wk)	156	6.15±3.06	5.99±3.22	0.494*
Sedentary behaviour (weekend day) (min/wk)	164	4.99±2.92	4.86±2.60	0.598*
Fruit, >1 portion/d	196	143(72.96)	135(68.88)	0.243†
Vegetables, >1 portion/d	196	109(55.61)	106(54.08)	0.779†
Having breakfast, >5 d/wk	192	171(89.06)	162(84.38)	0.093†
Alcohol, 2 times/wk or more	196	45(22.96)	40(20.41)	0.383†
Smoking, yes	186	21(11.29)	26(13.98)	0.125†
Depressive symptoms (PHQ-8 ≥10)	173	27(15.61)	24(13.87)	0.629†
Sleep problems (score range 0-10)‡	194	4.02±2.87	4.40±3.05	0.058*
Fatigue (score range 0-10)‡	193	4.34±2.73	4.50±2.78	0.433*
Medication adherence (SMAQ), no adherence	139	82(58.99)	67(48.20)	0.033†
HR-QoL				
PCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100)§	163	49.33±8.79	50.37±8.60	0.032*
MCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100)§	163	44.74±9.93	45.41±8.49	0.329*
EQ-5D-5L utility values#	192	0.82±0.14	0.85±0.14	<.001*
EQ-5D-5L Overall health (score range 0-100)§	177	72.94±19.51	74.58±17.29	0.200*

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

Range from less than 0 (where 0 is the value of a health state equivalent to dead; negative values representing values worse than dead) to 1 (the value of full health), with higher scores indicating higher health utility.
Abbreviations: CDSE-6, short 6-item Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument; HR-QoL, Health-related quality of life; PHQ-8, 8-item Patient Health Questionnaire; SMAQ, short 6-item Medication Adherence Questionnaire; MCS, Mental Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; PCS, Physical Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; SF-12, 12-item Short form

Supplemental Table 4h. Spain - Self-management, healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, medication adherence and HR-QoL of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up (n=343)

	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Self-management				
CDSE-6 (score range 1-10) [§]	277	7.58±2.15	7.72±2.06	0.277*
Lifestyle factors				
Physical exercise				
Stretching/strengthening (min/wk)	309	42.91±61.12	43.25±60.01	0.926*
Aerobic exercise (min/wk)	336	131.56±115.97	124.02±114.74	0.217*
Walk for exercise (min/wk)	324	90.79±64.84	85.74±65.04	0.198*
Swimming or aquatic exercise (min/wk)	285	5.53±23.45	8.37±30.84	0.137*
Bicycling (min/wk)	288	9.79±32.26	8.49±28.43	0.421*
Other aerobic exercise (min/wk)	294	31.02±67.12	26.84±67.88	0.280*
Sedentary behaviour (week day) (min/wk)	309	4.11±2.62	4.01±2.43	0.567*
Sedentary behaviour (weekend day) (min/wk)	303	4.39±2.62	4.27±2.53	0.440*
Fruit, >1 portion/d	330	179(54.24)	177(53.64)	0.917†
Vegetables, >1 portion/d	326	82(25.15)	68(20.86)	0.131†
Having breakfast, >5 d/wk	320	305(95.31)	298(93.13)	0.143†
Alcohol, 2 times/wk or more	328	55(16.77)	51(15.55)	0.571†
Smoking, yes	328	71(21.65)	68(20.73)	0.581†
Depressive symptoms (PHQ-8 ≥10)	274	56(20.44)	55(20.07)	1.000†
Sleep problems (score range 0-10) [‡]	328	3.38±2.91	3.98±3.16	<.001*
Fatigue (score range 0-10) [‡]	318	3.41±3.12	3.65±3.21	0.130*
Medication adherence (SMAQ), no adherence	251	122(48.61)	111(44.22)	0.242†
HR-QoL				
PCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) [§]	251	44.45±11.14	44.31±11.09	0.797*
MCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) [§]	251	47.56±9.13	48.04±9.28	0.411*
EQ-5D-5L utility values [#]	314	0.55±0.22	0.54±0.24	0.289*
EQ-5D-5L Overall health (score range 0-100) [§]	323	72.27±20.74	71.46±21.49	0.468*

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

Range from less than 0 (where 0 is the value of a health state equivalent to dead; negative values representing values worse than dead) to 1 (the value of full health), with higher scores indicating higher health utility.

Abbreviations: CDSE-6, short 6-item Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument; HR-QoL, Health-related quality of life; PHQ-8, 8-item Patient Health Questionnaire; SMAQ, short 6-item Medication Adherence Questionnaire; MCS, Mental Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; PCS, Physical Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; SF-12, 12-item Short form

Supplemental Table 4i. United Kingdom - Self-management, healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, medication adherence and HR-QoL of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up (n=275)

	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Self-management				
CDSE-6 (score range 1-10) [§]	274	5.73±2.21	6.44±2.09	<.001*
Lifestyle factors				
Physical exercise				
Stretching/strengthening (min/wk)	274	31.04 ±57.23	24.53±42.83	0.038*
Aerobic exercise (min/wk)	275	128.73±117.42	130.53±123.84	0.800*
Walk for exercise (min/wk)	273	87.75±67.01	83.19±67.66	0.238*
Swimming or aquatic exercise (min/wk)	274	10.29±34.75	10.89±34.31	0.778*
Bicycling (min/wk)	275	6.27±22.58	9.65±31.14	0.067*
Other aerobic exercise (min/wk)	275	24.44±54.08	26.78±54.48	0.562*
Sedentary behaviour (week day) (min/wk)	268	6.71±3.30	6.21±2.71	0.009*
Sedentary behaviour (weekend day) (min/wk)	272	6.75±3.44	6.33±2.70	0.027*
Fruit, >1 portion/d	275	113(41.09)	104(37.82)	0.281†
Vegetables, >1 portion/d	272	101(37.13)	107(39.34)	0.525†
Having breakfast, >5 d/wk	273	197(72.16)	173(63.37)	0.002†
Alcohol, 2 times/wk or more	274	74(27.01)	54(19.71)	0.003†
Smoking, yes	272	12(4.41)	10(3.68)	0.727†
Depressive symptoms (PHQ-8 ≥10)	253	79(31.23)	63(24.90)	0.049†
Sleep problems (score range 0-10) [‡]	275	5.44±2.87	4.99±2.95	0.002*
Fatigue (score range 0-10) [‡]	275	5.71±2.84	5.41±2.75	0.040*
Medication adherence (SMAQ), no adherence	249	154(61.85)	165(66.27)	0.272
HR-QoL				
PCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) [§]	250	38.69±11.53	40.96±11.03	<.001*
MCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) [§]	250	41.96±10.31	43.17±9.54	0.069*
EQ-5D-5L utility values [#]	274	0.69±0.30	0.72±0.25	0.025*
EQ-5D-5L Overall health (score range 0-100) [§]	275	60.27±23.14	68.09±22.00	<.001*

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

Range from less than 0 (where 0 is the value of a health state equivalent to dead; negative values representing values worse than dead) to 1 (the value of full health), with higher scores indicating higher health utility.

Abbreviations: CDSE-6, short 6-item Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument; HR-QoL, Health-related quality of life; PHQ-8, 8-item Patient Health Questionnaire; SMAQ, short 6-item Medication Adherence Questionnaire; MCS, Mental Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; PCS, Physical Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; SF-12, 12-item Short form

ANNEX 4 OBJECTIVE 1: TABLES PER COVID-19 OUTBREAK

In Supplemental Table 4j, the results of objective 1 are shown stratified by participants filling in the follow-up questionnaire before or after the COVID-19 outbreak.

It shows that some effects were observed both before and after the COVID-19 outbreak (increase in self-management and in three of the four HR-QoL measures). We found significant improvements in total aerobic exercise (bicycling) and in vegetable intake only in participants who filled in the follow-up questionnaire after the outbreak; so the pandemic might resulted in improvements in these lifestyle behaviours. In contrast, in participants of before the outbreak, we found significant improvements in swimming, sedentary behaviour, alcohol use and health utility; this may indicate that the pandemic also resulted in negative effects on physical activity (more homebound) and alcohol use. An unexpected finding is that the decrease in depressive symptoms remained only significant in participants of after the outbreak; so the pandemic did not seem to increase depressive symptoms that quickly in our study sample.

Supplemental Table 4j. Self-management, healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, medication adherence and HR-QoL of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up, according to before/after COVID-19 outbreak (n=1189)

	Before COVID-19 outbreak				After COVID-19 outbreak			
	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Self-management								
CDSE-6 (score range 1-10) §	737	6.69±2.17	6.98±2.06	<.001*	336	6.73±2.10	7.02±2.05	0.006*
Lifestyle factors								
Physical exercise								
Stretching/strengthening (min/wk)	748	37.82±61.71	37.86±57.50	0.985*	344	37.06±59.98	33.79±54.58	0.300*
Aerobic exercise (min/wk)	803	150.52±122.40	148.58±121.11	0.640*	370	151.46±124.88	164.39±136.85	0.038*
Walk for exercise (min/wk)	781	95.80±66.45	92.71±66.69	0.216*	362	94.06±67.56	93.07±67.34	0.770*
Swimming or aquatic exercise (min/wk)	710	7.52±28.64	11.56±34.92	0.002*	338	10.25±33.96	10.34±35.07	0.955*
Bicycling (min/wk)	720	23.35±50.19	23.00±49.62	0.803*	341	21.55±45.19	29.91±56.44	0.001*
Other aerobic exercise (min/wk)	727	30.04±61.69	26.86±56.83	0.185*	341	30.66±62.42	35.10±71.62	0.246*
Sedentary behaviour (week day) (min/wk)	729	5.83±3.33	5.47±3.06	0.001*	340	6.34±3.23	6.04±3.07	0.064*
Sedentary behaviour (weekend day) (min/wk)	739	5.57±3.17	5.21±2.78	0.001*	336	6.24±3.32	5.96±2.97	0.090*
Fruit, >1 portion/d	802	438(54.61)	404(50.37)	0.017†	369	171(46.34)	178(48.24)	0.476†
Vegetables, >1 portion/d	797	317(39.77)	306(38.39)	0.483†	365	121(33.15)	141(38.63)	0.031†
Having breakfast, >5 d/wk	785	653(83.18)	642(81.78)	0.367†	356	265(74.44)	278(78.09)	0.093†
Alcohol, 2 times/wk or more	800	200(25.00)	169(21.13)	0.002†	368	82(22.28)	77(20.92)	0.511†
Smoking, yes	786	102(12.98)	101(12.85)	1.000†	361	55(15.24)	55(15.24)	1.000†
Depressive symptoms (PHQ-8 ≥10)	699	167(23.89)	148(21.17)	0.110†	329	81(24.62)	62(18.84)	0.021†
Sleep problems (score range 0-10) †	801	4.39±3.04	4.43±3.08	0.680*	360	4.47±2.99	4.46±3.01	0.938*
Fatigue (score range 0-10) †	789	4.76±3.01	4.67±2.94	0.316*	361	4.80±3.12	4.66±3.07	0.309*
Medication adherence (SMAQ), no adherence	601	344(57.24)	328(54.58)	0.264†	276	157(56.88)	151(54.71)	0.566†
HR-QoL								
PCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) §	695	43.47±11.39	44.42±10.93	0.001*	311	44.17±11.23	45.20±10.99	0.024*

MCS Score (SF-12; score range 0-100) §	695	43.93±10.19	45.46±9.27	<.001*	311	42.85±9.80	43.98±9.71	0.046*
EQ-5D-5L utility values#	783	0.68±0.27	0.70±0.26	0.002*	364	0.73±0.24	0.73±0.24	0.450*
EQ-5D-5L Overall health (score range 0-100)§	777	67.45±21.68	70.70±20.21	<.001*	359	68.59±21.02	70.22±20.36	0.040*

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

Range from less than 0 (where 0 is the value of a health state equivalent to dead; negative values representing values as worse than dead) to 1 (the value of full health), with higher scores indicating higher health utility.

Abbreviations: CDSE-6, short 6-item Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument; HR-QoL, Health-related quality of life; PHQ-8, 8-item Patient Health Questionnaire; SMAQ, short 6-item Medication Adherence Questionnaire; MCS, Mental Component Summary summarized by the SF-12; PCS, Physical Component Summary summarized by the SF-12SF-12, 12-item Short form

ANNEX 5 OBJECTIVE 2: TABLES PER PILOT SITE

In Supplemental Table 5c to 5g, the results of objective 2 are shown for each pilot site. Due to the smaller sample size for each pilot site, the significance of the findings should be interpreted with caution.

Participants of the Netherlands experienced significantly fewer medical errors but the other changes were not significant (Supplemental Table 5c). For France participants, communication with healthcare providers improved as well as understanding of health information (Supplemental Table 5d). No significant changes were found for Italian participants (Supplemental Table 5e). Participants of Spain understood their healthcare provider's explanation better and experienced fewer medical errors (Supplemental Table 5f). Last, UK participants reported improvements in their ability to find health information, in their understanding of health information and in communication with healthcare providers (Supplemental Table 5g).

Supplemental Table 5c. the Netherlands - Health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up (n=247)

	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Health literacy (HLQ)				
Ability to find good health information (score range 1-5) †	70	1.86±0.67	1.77±0.75	0.230*
Understand health information well enough to know what to do (score range 1-5) †	72	2.01±0.68	2.01±0.74	1.000*
Communication with healthcare providers (score range 0-5) §	79	2.44±1.17	2.57±1.33	0.233*
Prevalence of experienced medical errors				
Your healthcare provider did not explain this in a way you understood, % yes	81	26(31.10)	17(20.99)	0.108†
Personally experienced a medical error in your own care, % yes	82	24(29.27)	4(4.88)	<.001†
The medical error is a minor/major problem for you, % yes	10#	8(80.00)	4(40.00)	0.125†

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

Abbreviations: HLQ, Health literacy questionnaire

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

High number of missing data on this question because this is a sub-question (only for those who experienced an error)

Supplemental Table 5d. France - Health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up (n=124)

	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Health literacy (HLQ)				
Ability to find good health information (score range 1-5) †	86	2.37±0.96	2.14±0.95	0.023*
Understand health information well enough to know what to do (score range 1-5) †	87	2.21±0.81	1.98±0.94	0.009*
Communication with healthcare providers (score range 0-5) §	120	1.97±1.18	2.18±1.29	0.033*
Prevalence of experienced medical errors				
Your healthcare provider did not explain this in a way you understood, % yes	117	34(29.06)	37(31.62)	0.719†
Personally experienced a medical error in your own care, % yes	112	34(30.36)	28(25.00)	0.210†
The medical error is a minor/major problem for you, % yes	24#	23(95.83)	23(95.83)	1.000†

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

Abbreviations: HLQ, Health literacy questionnaire

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold
 † P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold
 ‡ A lower score is better
 § A higher score is better
 # High number of missing data on this question because this is a sub-question (only for those who experienced an error)

Supplemental Table 5e. Italy - Health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up (n=200)

	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Health literacy (HLQ)				
Ability to find good health information (score range 1-5) ‡	127	1.80±0.73	1.90±0.69	0.096*
Understand health information well enough to know what to do (score range 1-5) ‡	129	1.67±0.69	1.67±0.56	1.000*
Communication with healthcare providers (score range 0-5) §	180	2.09±1.22	2.23±1.32	0.112*
Prevalence of experienced medical errors				
Your healthcare provider did not explain this in a way you understood, % yes	183	59(32.24)	54(29.51)	0.568†
Personally experienced a medical error in your own care, % yes	180	45(25.00)	48(26.67)	0.775†
The medical error is a minor/major problem for you, % yes	26#	20(76.92)	23(88.46)	0.375†

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

Abbreviations: HLQ, Health literacy questionnaire

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold
 † P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold
 ‡ A lower score is better
 § A higher score is better
 # High number of missing data on this question because this is a sub-question (only for those who experienced an error)

Supplemental Table 5f. Spain - Health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up (n=343)

	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Health literacy (HLQ)				
Ability to find good health information (score range 1-5) ‡	192	1.81±0.73	1.85±0.69	0.512*
Understand health information well enough to know what to do (score range 1-5) ‡	208	1.84±0.71	1.76±0.67	0.138*
Communication with healthcare providers (score range 0-5) §	310	1.78±1.29	1.89±1.36	0.118*
Prevalence of experienced medical errors				
Your healthcare provider did not explain this in a way you understood, % yes	319	92(28.84)	73(22.88)	0.046 †
Personally experienced a medical error in your own care, % yes	261	75(28.74)	35(13.41)	<.001 †
The medical error is a minor/major problem for you, % yes	40#	32(80.00)	28(70.00)	0.424†

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

Abbreviations: HLQ, Health literacy questionnaire

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold
 † P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold
 ‡ A lower score is better
 § A higher score is better
 # High number of missing data on this question because this is a sub-question (only for those who experienced an error)

Supplemental Table 5g. United Kingdom - Health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up (n=275)

	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
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Health literacy (HLQ)				
Ability to find good health information (score range 1-5) ‡	246	1.95±0.83	1.82±0.70	0.010*
Understand health information well enough to know what to do (score range 1-5) ‡	241	2.05±0.82	1.89±0.74	0.008*
Communication with healthcare providers (score range 0-5) §	273	2.25±1.32	2.52±1.14	<.001*
Prevalence of experienced medical errors				
Your healthcare provider did not explain this in a way you understood, % yes	273	113(41.39)	102(37.36)	0.300†
Personally experienced a medical error in your own care, % yes	273	67(24.54)	55(20.15)	0.097†
The medical error is a minor/major problem for you, % yes	43#	39(90.70)	37(86.05)	0.625†

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

Abbreviations: HLQ, Health literacy questionnaire

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

High number of missing data on this question because this is a sub-question (only for those who experienced an error)

ANNEX 6 OBJECTIVE 2: TABLES PER COVID-19 OUTBREAK

In Supplemental Table 5j, the results of objective 2 are shown stratified by participants filling in the follow-up questionnaire before or after the COVID-19 outbreak.

Some effects were observed both before and after the COVID-19 outbreak (improvement in communication with healthcare provider and fewer medical errors experienced). We found a borderline significant improvement in the understanding of healthcare provider only in participants who filled in the follow-up questionnaire after the outbreak. In contrast, only in participants of before the outbreak, we found a significant improvement in the understanding of health information to know what to do. These findings indicate that the pandemic did not consistently affect the effects on health literacy and experience of medical errors.

Supplemental Table 5j. Health literacy, communication with healthcare providers and experienced medical errors of participants of the CDSMP intervention at baseline and at 6-months follow-up, according to before/after COVID-19 outbreak (n=1189)

	Before COVID-19 outbreak				After COVID-19 outbreak			
	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value	n (paired)	Baseline	Follow-up	P-value
Health literacy (HLQ)								
Ability to find good health information (score range 1-5) ‡	486	1.95±0.81	1.87±0.74	0.095*	235	1.89±0.79	1.85±0.73	0.382*
Understand health information well enough to know what to do (score range 1-5) ‡	502	1.91±0.75	1.81±0.70	0.002*	235	1.99±0.80	1.90±0.77	0.130*
Communication with healthcare providers (score range 0-5) §	664	2.06±1.22	2.26±1.31	<.001*	298	2.02±1.28	2.15±1.31	0.042*
Prevalence of experienced medical errors								
Your healthcare provider did not explain this in a way you understood, % yes	663	217(32.73)	195(29.41)	0.128†	310	107(34.52)	88(28.39)	0.056†
Personally experienced a medical error in your own care, % yes	624	168(26.92)	111(17.79)	<.001†	284	77(27.11)	59(20.77)	0.042†
The medical error is a minor/major problem for you, % yes	93	79(84.95)	78(83.87)	1.000†	50	43(86.00)	37(74.00)	0.109†

Note: Presented as mean±SD or N(%); n (paired) indicates the number of participants with data on the outcome at both baseline and follow-up

Abbreviations: HLQ, Health literacy questionnaire

* P-value based on paired T test; significant P-values in bold

† P-value based on McNemar test; significant P-values in bold

‡ A lower score is better

§ A higher score is better

High number of missing data on this question because this is a sub-question (only for those who experienced an error)